

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI LECCE

DIPARTIMENTO DI INGEGNERIA DELL'INNOVAZIONE

Ph.D Thesis in Information Engineering
(ING-INF05)

XVIII Ph.D cycle

**A Framework to Generate Heterogeneous
Collaborative Web Environments**

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SEPTEMBER 2006

A Elisa

The use of cyberspace to overcome the expense of travel and to overcome the physical limitations of reality has sparked the imagination of many visionary

Sandeep Singhal and Michael Zyza (Networked Virtual Environments)

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Abstract

*A Collaborative Virtual Environment, CVE, is a computer-based virtual space that supports collaborative work and social interplay. In a **3D CVE**, a "hosting" **3D world** is the necessary ingredient: within it, users, provided with graphical embodiments, called avatars, that convey their identity (presence, location, movement, ..) can meet and interact with other users, with agents, or with virtual objects.*

Even if graphics hardware and 3D technologies are rapidly evolving and the increased internet connection speed allows to share amount of data and information between user geographically distributed, the development of networked three-dimensional applications is still complicated and demands expert knowledge. Though some collaborative Web 3D technologies and applications had already been developed, most of them are concerned especially to offer an high level realistic representation of the virtual world as increasing the level of detail would mean to increase the "virtual presence" sense in the 3D world; at the same time they don't support from one hand an high level, non-expert authoring process, from the other the concept of programming flexibility and of component reuse is rarely taken into account.

In my thesis, we advocate the need of drastically simplify authoring and personalization phases through formal description of the interaction's sets as well as of the behavioral features and rules, that we call "collaborative metaphors", in a component oriented fashion to drive collaboration among users in the specific way a designer is intended to do. As result of previous considerations we present WebTalk04 (WT04), a declarative 3D component framework based on XML documents describing not only the environment formal structure of the virtual world where the action take place but also the complex interaction set of rules that control interactions between users and world objects used to stimulate certain kind of collaboration, thus effectively help fast prototyping and an easy building up of such collaborative applications. The WT04 framework also provide a runtime 3D rendering engine fully configurable through XML in order to easily modify virtual world settings as well as collaborative interaction rules thus allowing to control independently geometries, behaviors and contents, assigning to different developer (i.e software dev. , content dev. , graphics dev. , session designers) different task.

Main innovative features of the proposed framework are:

- Decouple all phases of the authoring process*
- Easily define and compose virtual sessions in a component oriented fashion*
- Drive and control interaction among user to stimulate specific kinds of collaboration*

Moreover, even though Collaborative Virtual Environments are one of the most successful applications in the field of Computer Supported Collaborative Workgroup (CSCW), their support and working environment has often been relegated to desktop systems without regarding of recent spread of smart mobile devices and wireless networks. In this work, we also present the extension of the WebTalk framework to support in a flexible way both stationary and mobile systems. We explore the use of heterogeneous collaboration through a software architecture, running on mobile devices compatible with J2ME, able to configure itself on the basis of a XML declaration representing workspace and interaction rules shared with the 3D stationary users.

PART 1

Objectives

The target of this Research work is to explore the nature of the remote collaboration between more persons, involved in the same activity, using work tools interconnected through the Internet.

Our goal was the definition of conceptual models that allow to describe the manner in which this collaboration occurs, and to devise which are the best modalities to support it, regardless of the specific technology used.

In particular, one of my first aims was to explore how to express the collaboration between two or more remote users using a 3D representation of the collaboration context, through the design of a software framework for the support of collaboration on the web called **WebTalk**.

The definition of general models through which to handle the problem of the collaboration between remote users has to go through the experimental developing of prototypes, that allow to effectively make remote collaboration sessions.

From a conceptual point of view, in WebTalk I proposed some models that give a guide in the analysis and design of a 3D collaborative system. These models show how the collaboration between users occurs and according to which canons it can be regulated and directed (collaborative metaphors' model); how to organize the three-dimensional space to make it structured and navigable; how to make the 3D space can be used as a space of access to bi-dimensional contents (picture, text, audio, video) collected in a traditional web site.

From a more technical point of view, my work focused on the design and subsequent development of a framework, called WebTalk04 (WT04), to support this remote collaboration: a general and totally configurable (through XML) engine that allows to build 3D Virtual Environments starting from a repository of available geometric forms, to assign to each one a specific behaviour according to the particular virtual experience (learning, training, virtual meetings,..) wanted.

WT04 system has some innovative features among which there are:

- *Three tier fully configurable framework, based on MVC pattern*

- *WT04 declarative model (scene graph based)*
- *Access control and behaviors (scripting language)*
- *3D CVE: WebTalk04 software platform*

Another important goal was to allow WT04 engine to handle different devices (PDA, SmartPhones, etc.) making them to interoperate together and finding the most correct collaboration paradigm able to support this kind of heterogeneous interaction.

1 Collaborative Systems

In this chapter it's defined the context, the structure of the thesis, as well as the proposed objectives.

1.1 Introduction

Groupware or **collaborative environments** are defined as any environment used by some number of concurrent users located elsewhere, that perform tasks in cooperation to achieve common goals. Moreover, it provides a way of interaction between these users and the shared scenario. The **CSCW** (*Computer Supported Cooperative Work*) term was coined to reference such software, although there is some blurring between the different meaning of the terms collaborative and cooperative. Though both these terms are used as synonyms, there are some subtle distinctions. **Cooperation** and **collaboration** do not differ in terms of whether or not the task is distributed, but by virtue of the way in which the task is divided. In cooperation the task is split (hierarchically) into independent subtasks. In collaboration, processes may be (hierarchically) divided into intertwined layers. In cooperation, coordination is only required when assembling partial results, while collaboration is a coordinated, synchronous activity that is the result of a continued attempt to construct and maintain a shared conception of a problem.

There exist a vast number of different collaborative environments, each of them bringing its own vision, with a set of **collaborative tools**. Such tools may be classified into three different types according to the **time frame** and **user's presence**: those that involve asynchronous communication (email or discussion forums), those that involve synchronous communication, meaning that users must be connected to collaborate (chat or instant messaging), and finally those that support both synchronous and asynchronous group activity, like electronic calendars, where events and important dates are signalled.

In the last years we have experienced a huge leap in communication technologies. The augment of network bandwidth has promoted world wide resource sharing and thus enabling novel killer applications which have boosted Internet's use. BSCW¹ and Groove² are two significant examples of collaboration-oriented tools, which follow the workspace concept. BSCW is a classic in the collaborative environments software, and as with many others, it is based on client-server web technology. It allows workspace sharing between different users. On the other hand, Groove is a shared desktop application including file

sharing services, messages, chat, synchronized web browsing, or calendar. It is based on a peer-to-peer (P2P) architecture, meaning that it does not rely on a single server.

Three-dimensional (3D) virtual environments were conceived a long time ago and have also evolved as different applications, like simulators, 3D chats or videogames.

3D Virtual worlds' origins are found in military simulation, more precisely in flight simulators. Consequently, public commercialization of such technology was open to all audiences, and originated the model which is still valid nowadays: 3D graphics in immersive environments trying to offer more degrees of freedom within the virtual scenario. Besides networking advances, existing systems are gaining in computing power as well as in graphics technology. Consequently, **Collaborative Virtual Environments (CVEs)** are the next step in collaborative applications, since their aim is to change the way in which we perform our daily work, study, play, communicate, or, in general, *interact with others*.

1.2 Background

Collaborative virtual environments have been appeared under several different guises: CVEs, networked VEs (NVE or NET-VE), collaborative workspaces (CWs), and many others; however, they all take on the same generic tasks, albeit for different purposes. The first real system to emerge as a collaborative environment (leaving aside hardware dedicated systems and text-based multi-user dungeons, MUDs) was called "Reality Built for Two"³ and featured a simple two-person connection to the same machine. Since then there have been a multitude of systems developed, with popularity peaking around 1997 with new developments generally falling off ever since. Figure 1⁴ demonstrates this trend, providing a chronological list of publications that have featured some kind of CVE technology. Different versions (not republications) of each system have also been included in order that developments and improvements can easily be visualized.

Figure 1 - A chronological ordering of publications on collaborative virtual environments (the bars indicate the approximate number of unique articles).

Let us discuss what we consider the basic foundations of collaborative virtual environments. Firstly, **3D virtual worlds** provide the three-dimensional view, and secondly, **distributed systems** are necessary to offer multi-user and collaborative tools capabilities.

1.2.1 Three-Dimensional Virtual Worlds

A 3D virtual world can be seen as an environment where not only the appearance but its components' inner representation belongs to a three-dimensional space. A virtual world provides a way for the users to interact. For example, modifying its components, interacting with them, etc.

Additionally, these modifications must be autonomous, allowing the user itself to decide what kind of interaction to choose. Therefore, it is an immersive environment, meaning that user is capable of recognizing that he is inside a 3D environment, assimilating all temporal and spatial aspects related to it. Such environments need to work in real time, requiring good response times, so that users do not notice lags between actions and the immediate effect which affects

their context. Lastly, it must be a realistic environment, where appearance quality must reflect as much as possible the real world.

1.2.2 Distributed Systems

Distributed computing studies the coordinated use of physically separated computers. As stated by Andrew S. Tanenbaum, “Distributed systems need radically different software than centralized systems do.” Independent of its architecture or the coupling degree between the different network members, we want to highlight the **event propagation service** and **persistence service**, which we consider as key services for application development on top of these environments. They provide necessary abstractions to disseminate and store the system’s state in multi-user collaborative applications.

Both of the dominant distributed systems’ architectural approaches are discussed as follows:

a) *Client-Server Model*

This is the classic and most used model, because it the easiest to implement. There are just two types of different entities: the server, which offers all services, and client, which uses them. In this model, all services, like state propagation or data persistence, are offered by the server itself, being responsible to propagate and store information.

When a server is unable to withstand system’s load, more servers can be added, adopting clustering strategies or server federation techniques, mainly depending on the local or remote machines location. In either case, adoption of these strategies implies an economic overhead, charged to institution which hosts the servers.

b) *Decentralized Models*

The alternative to the previous model is decentralization.

The idea is that all components in the distributed system have the same responsibilities acting both as clients and servers. These systems also satisfy the following features:

- **Load balancing.** It is not necessary to calculate a priori the systems' capacity depending on working peaks. Capacity can be reassigned on demand.
- **High availability.** They are fault tolerant because if a node fails, services are immediately rescheduled to another network node.
- **Low cost.** The services offered by these architectures are managed in a way that obviates the need for powerful servers.
- The most wide-known decentralized models available nowadays are the **Grid** (Global Resource Information Database) and the **peer-to-peer model**.

1.3 Collaborative Virtual Environments

As we explained in the previous section, the virtual worlds evolved to multi-user virtual environments using distributed systems technology. Moreover, we can consider Distributed Virtual Environments as the origin of Collaborative Virtual Environments. To better understand such environments, we present a group of key requirements that are necessary to build such multi-user applications.

1.3.1 Requirements

a) Session Administration and Zone

To determine the structure of the environment we can use the **zone** concept. A zone is a part of the virtual environment where users can interact and use the different available objects. However, when there are many state changes in a short period (movements, actions, arrivals and departures), the system reach a state where it cannot meet the requirements in real time.

Here is where it becomes necessary to use mechanisms such as **zone partitioning**, reducing the virtual space and the number of users, so decrementing the maximum number of simultaneous events needing to be processed. A very simple algorithm consists on discarding the events at a distance threshold from us.

b) Shared Objects and State Propagation

Another essential concept is the explicit support of shared objects. Usually, users engage in collaborative interactions with other users in the shared context,

or with accessible collaborative components. These collaborative components, also called artefacts, range from synchronous to asynchronous, depending on the interaction time frame.

There are many types of artefacts e.g. voting tools, slide presenter tools, documents, audio/video players, etc.

To ensure the state propagation required to guarantee the persistence in the overall system, each change should be spread and later on persisted to be properly restored in another moment. This is one of the biggest problems in distributed systems because these systems must maintain the state of the components in the virtual environment in a seamless and coordinated way.

c) *Coordination and Consistency*

Another feature that should be present in any collaborative environment is the explicit support for coordination policies. These policies can be categorized in roles for access control and concurrency control. The platform should provide extension hooks to insert custom coordination components.

The concurrency control mechanism should provide mutual exclusion services for shared artefacts, so that the users do not produce inconsistencies in the use of these tools.

An example to illustrate this problem could be the transport of an artefact from one zone to another of the virtual world.

d) *Awareness*

Awareness is another important feature in the virtual environments. We can define it as an understanding of the activities of others, which provides a context of your own activity. An awareness platform should provide data acquisition from the running environment. The importance of a well-defined awareness model must be emphasized.

1.3.2 Distributed Virtual Environments

Distributed Virtual Environments are the bridge between virtual worlds and collaborative virtual environments. One of the firsts 3D distributed environments was **DIVE**⁵ (*Distributed Virtual Interactive Environment*), created in Sweden by SICS (*Swedish Institute of Computer Science*) in 1991. It provided representation

by avatars, different browsing and interaction types, and audio and video communication.

The DIVE environment consisted of a group of distributed processes that represented avatars or objects, which could modify the database that contained the representation of the world. The communication among these processes was based on multicast protocols and thus did not rely on a central server architecture. In fact, each user possessed a copy of the world in which they collaborated.

We can also find other simpler examples, such as 3D chat communities like **ActiveWorlds**⁶. It belongs to a company located in Massachusetts, USA, that provides a platform and the necessary software to interact with other users in a 3D environment. ActiveWorlds also gives the possibility to rent a space in its server so that the user manages his own world.

1.3.3 Collaborative 3D Frameworks

After DIVE, other environments like SPLINE⁷, NPSNET⁸ or MASSIVE⁹ appeared. Many of them have successfully solved problems like the structuring of the world and the zone partitioning, the state propagation, the coordination and the consistency, and the awareness. They also introduced concepts like the portals between worlds, to be able to move between them.

Those collaborative environments offered richer user interactions by means of flexible collaboration tools. Nevertheless, the complexity of the domain has led to huge and intricate software systems that are difficult to extend and reuse, so precluding system interoperability and flexibility.

To cope with these problems, the trend is to augment modularization in the design of such infrastructures. Many systems are following a framework-based approach to augment modularization and provide extension points to develop new applications on top of them.

In the domain that we are studying, we highlight two examples of framework-oriented platforms enabling the development of collaborative virtual applications. One example is **Ants CSCW**¹⁰, a generic multi-user collaborative framework. The ANTS system is a component-based application framework that simplifies development of distributed collaborative components in the Java language. It

provides a client side container for JavaBean components that hides complexity from middleware layers by providing a remote persistent property mechanism and a distributed event service. The key architectural decision of creating the distributed event service on top of a publish/subscribe notification system permits a very powerful and flexible approach. On the one hand, state propagation is efficiently accomplished by the decoupled notification system.

On the other hand, a seamless awareness model is achieved that directly benefits from filtering capabilities offered by the messaging middleware.

Figure 2 - Students Watching a Video in MOVE.

MOVE (see Figure 2) is a Collaborative Virtual Environment constructed on top of the ANTS component groupware framework. The system fully benefits from the underlying collaborative services provided by the ANTS infrastructure. MOVE provides essential collaborative services like shared sessions, support for synchronous and asynchronous components, security, coordination and a server side awareness infrastructure. One of the key aspects of this work is to provide extensibility at all levels of the system. It is thus possible to create new components or artefacts, to develop new coordination mechanisms, to interface with different middleware services and propagation channels, and to develop new actuators for the awareness service. This creates an interesting playfield for research in Virtual Environments by opening the system to third-party extensions willing to solve specific problems in this wide domain.

Another framework, **Croquet**¹¹, provides a virtual environment enabling third-party development of collaborative tools. Croquet supports collaborative access to shared resources in a wide-area scale (see Figure 3). Croquet aims to provide an extensible substrate for the construction of collaborative virtual environments.

Figure 3 - Avatar Displaying Portals to Other Worlds in Croquet

The users and the user groups can build private or shared worlds and to make them accessible by means of interdimensional portals.

Croquet is based on a peer-to-peer system and uses replication mechanisms to guarantee the maintenance of the virtual world state. Also, if a machine client is too slow to compute the state, it is discarded for this task.

Both MOVE and Croquet represent academic approaches to the complex setting of collaborative virtual environments. None of them achieved to provide a simple extensible model attracting many third-party extensions. A lot of research work and commercial support is still required to produce a true killer application in the arena of 3D collaborative virtual environments.

1.4 CVEs Application Fields

To stress the utility of CVEs, we conclude by discussing three of their main application fields. We also enumerate example products and, in this way, we can see how research projects and commercial products are constructed, and how million-people communities can interact in a single virtual world.

1.4.1 Collaborative Work

When talking about collaborative environments, enterprise groupwork is one of the most common and interesting aspects to study. Working towards a common project, which can be divided into subtasks, is a definition which fits perfectly in the collaborative work field.

As an example to illustrate this section, we talk about **Workspace 3D**¹² from Tixeo, located in Montpellier, France. Workspace 3D offers a three-dimensional workspace where all enterprise members can talk together by video conference and collaborate in this environment represented by their avatar (see Figure 4). The environment provides portals where collaborative applications are loaded. Current tools are: slide projector, shared folders, desktop applications, whiteboard, shared browsing, and 3D model viewer. This is a proprietary solution, started from scratch, being an ad-hoc solution following the client-server model.

Figure 4 - Videoconference with Browser and Whiteboard in Workspace 3D.

1.4.2 Learning

The learning field is one of the most explored when innovating in the collaborative setting. This also applies to collaborative virtual environments where we can find interesting contributions. From these projects we highlight **MOVE**, initially designed to recreate collaborative virtual environments in the

learning scenario. MOVE distinguishes teacher and student roles and provides interesting tools like professor-guided navigation or moderation capabilities.

MOVE was used in medical educational settings and a whole hospital was recreated in the virtual world. Besides MOVE, there is the **NICE**¹³ (Narrative Based, Immersive, Constructionist/Collaborative Environment for Children) project from the University of Illinois, USA.

In this project, a virtual environment for children was created, enabling them to collaborate and talk between them. They can also find the teacher or other avatars controlled by the artificial intelligence of the system. The garden world is dealt in a persistent way, storing changes for next sessions.

One feature to highlight in this project is the utilization of virtual reality devices, like head mounted displays (HMD), and data-gloves within a CAVE¹⁴ environment.

1.4.3 Entertainment

Multiplayer games can be considered as a simple form of collaboration. Games have not only been one of the fundamental pillars for the development of graphical tools, but they are also one of the biggest focuses of virtual communities, since they have demonstrated that they can be used by more than five million users.

In *MMORPG* (Massive (ly) Online Multiplayer Network role-Playing Game) games, users can find a richer collaboration. This point is of special interest to us, not for the degree of collaboration, but for the great number of users that interact. It all began with **Ultima Online** and now hundreds of games of this kind already exist.

Nowadays, games like **Lineage II** or **World of Warcraft** (see Figure 5) are a good example of the success of these persistent virtual worlds. Normally, a monthly fee is needed to support server infrastructure maintenance for these games.

Figure 5 - Meeting in A Forest at World of Warcraft.

On the other hand, every videogame company supports the multiplayer service in their releases. However, in more homogeneous platforms, like video consoles, more global solutions are adopted.

One well-known solution which was started in 2003 for network based games in the Sony PlayStation 2 platform is the IBM Butterfly Grid, based on the OGSA (Open Grid Services Architecture). Butterfly controls the load of the server processes and when it determines that there are too many players connected to the same server, it automatically reconfigures servers with lesser use to support the most demanded games, and transfer players to these systems.

1.5 3D modeling and programming languages

During last recent years there have been several different approaches to the attempt of porting 3D on the web. Omitting to report trends lo longer supported, as for example 3DML and its most famous application FlatLand¹⁵, we will refer to VRML and its successor X3D as real modeling languages, and to Java3D as example of programming language 3D oriented.

1.5.1 VRML

VRML, the *Virtual Reality Modeling Language*, is a file format for describing interactive three-dimensional objects and *worlds*.

VRML is not a programming language like JAVA, nor is it a "Markup Language" like HTML. It is a modeling language, which means you use it to describe 3D scenes. It's more complex than HTML, but less complex (except for the scripting capability) than a programming language. Here a world is a model of a 3D space, which can contain 3D objects, lights, and backgrounds; in other 3D systems this is often called a *scene*. Objects can be built from solid shapes, from text, or from primitive points, lines, and faces. Objects have optical material properties which affects how they interact with the lights in the world; they can also have textures (2-D patterns) applied to them.

Objects can be grouped into more complex objects, used multiple times, translated, and rotated. Objects can trigger *events*, which can be routed to other events or to scripts written in JavaScript or Java. Within VRML you can trigger sounds, move objects along paths, and link to HTML or VRML targets. In JavaScript or Java you can manipulate VRML object properties programmatically and even generate new objects.

The experience for someone browsing a VRML world can be active or passive, depending on how you've scripted the world. VRML can be used to create interactive 3D games, simulations of real or imagined devices and buildings or even cities for walk-throughs, interactive visualizations of scientific data, advertising banners, art, music, and much more. VRML is a system- and device-independent language, so one VRML world can be viewed on any VRML viewer of the correct vintage. It's entirely possible to create VRML worlds with nothing more than the VRML specification, a text editor, and a VRML-enabled browser (all of which are free), with a good grasp of 3D computer graphics concepts. On the other hand, a VRML modeling program or *world builder* can take a *lot* of the pain out of the process, and make 3D world creation accessible to non-technical designers.

Figure 6 - Example of VRML 3D world

The current VRML specification is VRML97¹⁶, which is an ISO and IEC standard. VRML97 is essentially the same as VRML 2.0, which in turn is essentially the SGI "Moving Worlds" proposal. VRML 1.0 is pretty much obsolete at this point, although most VRML 2.0 browsers will automatically convert VRML 1.0 worlds.

VRML 1.0 allowed you to create static 3D worlds assembled from static objects, which could be hyperlinked to other worlds, as well as to HTML documents. Visitors of the worlds were able to "fly" or "walk" around the static objects, and the only way of interaction was possible by "clicking" on a hyperlinked object, which worked like a hyperlink on a www-page: dropped you to the target of the link.

In VRML 2.0 objects can be animated, and they can respond to both time-based and user-initiated events. VRML 2.0 also allows you to incorporate multimedia objects (for example sound and movies) in your scenes.

The new features can be grouped:

- Enhanced static worlds
 - sound node
 - extrusion node (actually a modeling tool that lets you create extrusions, surfaces of revolution, and shapes formed by bending, twisting, and tapering different types of curves)

VRML's roundabout path

1994-1995 San Francisco software engineers Tony Parisi and Mark Pesce spearhead an effort to standardize 3D on the Web.

1996 The VRML Consortium is formed.

1997 The ISO ratifies VRML 97.

1998 3D on the Web founders. Silicon Graphics shuts its Cosmo unit. Microsoft shelves its Chromeffects initiative.

1999 The VRML Consortium, in an effort to create a "commercially relevant" successor to VRML, regroups as the Web3D Consortium.

2000 The X3D working group is formed.

2002 An X3D draft is released.

- background node (lets you describe a background panorama for your scene, such as mountains, plains, or some other distant landscape, as well as color gradations for the sky and ground)
- fog node (you can create foggy atmospheres)
- new kind of texture node (allows you to show movie clips within your scene. Combining this movie texture node with the audio clip node provides you with true multimedia resources: video and sound)
- shape node (encapsulates both appearance and geometry: appearance properties are no longer inherited within the file resulting a simplified scene graph)
- Interaction
 - collision detection node (contains collision information> user can no longer walk through walls in the scene)
 - sensor nodes (they wait for a particular event to occur and then do something in response to that event. This way you can sense the user's presence at a particular area of the scene, and respond to it. For example, one kind of sensor can wait until the camera gets to a certain point in the scene and then trigger a change in part of the scene in response to the proximity of the user-perhaps by opening a door or turning on a light.)
- Animation and behavior scripting
 - interpolators (You can incorporate keyframe animations. You supply the object description at certain critical points, and then the interpolator performs the calculations for the in-between descriptions.)
 - script node (routines written in a programming language such as Netscape's JavaScript or Sun Microsystems' Java)
- Prototyping new VRML objects VRML comes with a fixed set of objects (called nodes). The prototyping feature lets you create complex objects that you can reuse, changing certain characteristics of the objects when desired.

- VRML File Information You can describe the defaults for the browser: navigation style(walk, fly, examine), the navigation speed, headlight on/off.

1.5.2 Java3D

Java3D is a low level 3D scene-graph based graphics programming API for the java language. It does not form part of the core APIs required by the Java specification. The class libraries exist under the javax.media.j3d top level package as well as utility classes provided in javax.vecmath.

A low level API provides routines for creation of 3D geometries in a scene graph structure that is independent of the underlying hardware implementation for realtime programming. The API provides scene graph compilation and other optimization techniques. It is heavily optimized towards the requirements of realtime 3D rendering and hence does not contain capabilities for photo-realistic rendering effects used to produce movie quality images (ie ray-tracing or radiosity based rendering algorithms).

The Java3D API consists of two parts: The API Specification and the implementation. Java3D mainly consists of the API specification. Anyone may implement the spec. Sun also provide an implementation of this specification but is encouraging 3rd party developers to implement J3D directly to the hardware.

Java 3D was designed with several goals in mind. Chief among them was high performance. Several design decision were made so that Java 3D implementations could deliver the highest level of performance to application users. In particular, when trade-offs were made, the alternative that benefited runtime execution was chosen.

Other important Java 3D goals:

- Provide a rich set of features for creating interesting 3D worlds, tempered by the need to avoid non-essential or obscure features. Features that could be layered on top of Java 3D were not included.
- Provide a high-level, object-oriented, programming paradigm that enables developers to rapidly deploy sophisticated applications and applets.
- Provide support for runtime loaders. This allows Java 3D to accommodate a wide variety of file formats, such as vendor-specific CAD formats, interchange formats, VRML 1.0, and VRML 2.0.

Java 3D's *scene graph*-based programming model provides a simple and flexible mechanism for representing and rendering scenes. The scene graph contains a complete description of the entire scene, or virtual universe. This includes the geometric data, the attribute information, and the viewing information needed to render the scene from a particular point of view.

Figure 7 - Sample of Java 3D Scene Graph

The Java 3D API improves on previous graphics APIs by eliminating many of the bookkeeping and programming chores that those APIs impose. Java 3D allows the programmer to think about geometric objects rather than about triangles-about the scene and its composition rather than about how to write the rendering code for efficiently displaying the scene.

Java 3D neither anticipates nor directly supports every possible 3D need. Instead it provides support to add those features through Java code.

Objects defined using a Computer Aided Design (CAD) system or an animation system may be included in a Java 3D-based application. Most such modeling packages have a (sometimes proprietary) external format. Designers can export to a file geometry designed using an external modeler. Java 3D can use that geometric information, but only if an application provides a means for reading and translating the modeler's file format into Java 3D primitives.

Similarly, VRML loaders will parse and translate VRML files and generate the appropriate Java 3D objects and Java code necessary to support the file's contents.

1.5.3 X3D

The new web 3D standard is X3D/ Extensible 3D. Open source libraries and commercial plugins have already been released in beta for this new standard. Exporters from commercial editors and dedicated editors are in development. Freeware editors are already available.

What features of X3D distinguish it from VRML97? According to Tony Parisi, from Media Machines Inc., the most important new features are the following :

- Multiple data encodings (XML, VRML "classic", Binary)
- New graphics features (NURBs, Humanoid Animation, Multitexturing, Triangle primitives, 2D shapes inside 3D)
- New networking features (LoadSensor, improved Inline)
- Improved APIs, more language/object model bindings (e.g. DOM) and many clarifications to event model for better conformance
- Modularity (the standard is broken up into profiles and components so it can be supported at many levels)
- MPEG-4 has streaming interactive 3D using VRML

Another important goal was to create specification which would allow the widest possible interoperability; that the worlds created would render and behave

identically in different implementations. VRML97 makes it 80% of the way to this goal, but that isn't good enough in a graphics app. For the VRML97 authors, getting identical rendering fidelity and behavioral fidelity from multiple browsers for the same world was difficult. Has this goal been met in X3D? Tony Parisi says that:

“We need to be careful: "identical" is a relative term. And the tolerances people have will vary greatly depending upon the target application. In a real-time game "identical" visuals may be less important than consistent behavior. In a CAD viewer the emphasis may be on pixel identity. etc.”

Given the early tests, it appears that this goal is close to being achieved, but it will take more time and practice to determine how close is close enough.

Work on the standard at the Web3D Consortium in partnership with ISO is ongoing. This relationship between ISO and the Web3D Consortium is one of the most successful and open of any involving ISO and a web standard. Richard Puk, the ISO/IEC JTC1/SC24 Liaison to the Web3D Consortium, says that the ISO and the Web3D Consortium have had a mutually successful relationship since the publication of the first Web3D-originated standard, VRML 97 (ISO/IEC 14772). This relationship is based on a formal Cooperative Agreement that satisfies the requirements and responsibilities of both organizations while ensuring timely standardization of Web3D Consortium specifications. The two organizations are in the final stages of standardizing X3D, a second generation of three-dimensional functionality for the...Web.

Why XML?

The original syntax for VRML 1.0 and VRML97 is the so-called curly bracket syntax familiar to C and C++ programmers. It is compact, has very fast parsing speed, and is context free. The following is an X3D example of a red sphere and a blue box lit by a directional light. This is an example of the new VRML Classic syntax.

```
#X3D V3.0 utf8
PROFILE IMMERSIVE
META "filename" "RedSphereBlueBox.wrl"

Transform (
  children [
    NavigationInfo (
      headlight FALSE
      avatarSize [ 0.25 1.6 0.75 ]
      type [ "EXAMINE" ]
    )
    DirectionalLight (
    )
    Transform (
      translation 3.0 0.0 1.0
      children [
        Shape (
          geometry Sphere ( radius 2.3
          )
          appearance Appearance (
            material Material ( diffuseColor 1.0 0.0 0.0
            )
          )
        )
      ]
    )
    Transform (
      translation -2.4 0.2 1.0
      rotation 0.0 0.707 0.707 0.9
      children [
        Shape (
          geometry Box (
          )
          appearance Appearance (
            material Material ( diffuseColor 0.0 0.0 1.0
            )
          )
        )
      ]
    )
  ]
)
```

Parsing speed was very important to early VRML work because performance is the *sine qua non* of real time animation. Given that RelaxNG sports a similar compact syntax, having syntax alternatives isn't that controversial in the XML world. While the decision to provide an XML syntax was quite controversial in the early days of designing the successor to VRML97, few dispute the wisdom of that decision today. According to Yumetech President, Alan Hudson, who is chair of the Web3D Open Source Working Group, the reasons are that

1. We need XML to interoperate with the Web
2. We need to incorporate new graphics technologies in a standardized way

3. We need VRML content to run the same across browsers
4. We need a standard which can evolve faster than every 5 years

While sharp eyed XML veterans will quickly note that XML cannot guarantee item three, the application of other XML application languages such as XSLT are considered sufficient reason to demand an XML encoding. The example above when encoded as XML looks like this:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="utf-8"?>
<!DOCTYPE X3D PUBLIC "ISO//Web3D//DTD X3D 3.0//EN"
  "http://www.web3d.org/specifications/x3d-3.0.dtd">

<X3D profile="IMMERSIVE"
  xmlns:xsd="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
  xsd:noNamespaceSchemaLocation="http://www.web3d.org/specifications/x3d-
<head>
  <meta name='filename' content='RedSphereBlueBox.x3d' />
</head>
<Scene>
  <Transform>
    <NavigationInfo headlight='false'
      avatarSize='0.25 1.6 0.75' type='EXAMINE' />
    <DirectionalLight />
    <Transform translation='3.0 0.0 1.0'>
      <Shape>
        <Sphere radius='2.3' />
        <Appearance>
          <Material diffuseColor='1.0 0.0 0.0' />
        </Appearance>
      </Shape>
    </Transform>
    <Transform translation='-2.4 0.2 1.0' rotation='0.0 0.707 0.707 0.9'>
      <Shape>
        <Box />
        <Appearance>
          <Material diffuseColor='0.0 0.0 1.0' />
        </Appearance>
      </Shape>
    </Transform>
  </Transform>
</Scene>
</X3D>
```

The rendering for the XML encoding looks like the following image:

Figure 8 - Sample of X3D rendered objects

1.6 Conclusions and Future Directions

Throughout this chapter we have analyzed different projects and standards, and we can now draw some conclusions. A logical one is that research projects experiment with more innovative approaches and technologies. This is the case of the system decentralization in **Croquet**. In stark contrast, commercial applications still deal with more traditional solutions (i.e. Workspace 3D).

These centralized solutions have proved to be insufficient in some cases, and enterprises sometimes cannot maintain infrastructures to support their products.

From a most specific web CVE point of view, due to considerable improvements in 3D graphics hardware and fast-evolving Internet technologies, the availability of 3D technologies for consumer platforms increases. As a result, the number of web-based three-dimensional applications in domains such as e-commerce, product presentations, entertainment, and virtual actors grows. By now a multitude of proprietary web 3D formats is available. This impedes standardization, particularly since most of the technologies are tailored to special application domains. VRML as the established Web3D graphics standard is

widely used. However, due to various problems it is rarely used for enabling applications such as e-commerce sites.

X3D as the VRML successor promises to be more successful due to the flexible XML-encoding, modularization through profiles and smarter 3D browsers. However, no single 3D technology (as Java3D for example) is expected to dominate the Web3D arena in the near future.

Nevertheless, 3D collaborative virtual environments are still less mature than their 2D counterparts. Some key reasons are the high cost of virtual reality devices, their overall bad quality and the costly expense of maintaining server farms for multi-user support. We expect that Collaborative Virtual Environments will reach the masses in the next few years thanks to advances in decentralized affordable technologies, low-cost virtual reality devices and probably with the help of less-intrusive mixed reality research.

PART 2

2 History of WebTalk

In this chapter we'll draw a chronological history of the development of the WebTalk system, starting from the first experiments of 3D visits in virtual museums in 1998 at the Hoc Laboratory of the Polytechnic of Milan

2.1 Introduction

Shared virtual environments, as collaboration tools, **CVE**, are mainly intended as a way to support collaboration of several users working on a common (virtual) scene (data model). Communication between instructors and trainees (simulation and training applications), sharing data (for visually supported discussions of scientists or decision-makers) (CSCW), support for innovative teaching-learning, support for collaborative e-learning (CSCL), are all examples of use for shared virtual environments. These applications (re)create a multi-user virtual world, according to Damer¹⁷, as two or three-dimensional graphical environments inhabited by users (represented as digital actors called “*avatar*”) that share with other users time, space and actions, cooperating together for a common goal.

Several different software systems, both commercial and research prototypes, support today Collaborative Virtual Environments. We started (in 1998) a development, WebTalk, which has evolved, over the years, to the current WebTalk04, described in the next chapter.

2.2 Previous projects and approaches

2.2.1 Virtual Leonardo

Our first original aim was to build a virtual museum where several visitors could “go together”. An application that allowed a virtual visit to the “*National Science and Technology Museum*”^{18 19 20} of Milan, was for some time available to the public, through the web site of the Museum itself. It hosted a 3D virtual exhibition on the machines “invented” by *Leonardo Da Vinci*, or more precisely, of wood machines built according to the drawings left by Leonardo. The application, award winner at **Museum&Web** international conference (New Orleans 1999), allowed the exploration of a building, vaguely representing the actual museum. A “guide”, playing the role of “Leonardo” had the task of guiding visitors through the virtual rooms. **Virtual objects** on display were either reproduction of Leonardo’s machines (on display in the museum) or gateways to web pages of the museum’s website. The

reproduction of the machines, rather than realistic was playful (also because most of Leonardo's machine do not work in reality).

Figure 9 - Scenes from the Virtual Leonardo application, an early experiment of collaboration within a virtual learning environment, with the aim to present Leonardo's work.

The prototype, called WebTalk-I and written in 1998, at the HOC laboratory of the Polytechnics of Milan, was mainly built with VRML and Java: it required a VRML Browser and a Java Virtual Machine to run a Java applet within the browser. The browsers (Netscape 4 and Explorer 4), at that time, had Java and a VRML plug-in installed by default, therefore the application was easily available for most PC users.

After six months of experimental usage, it was evident that cooperation (a loose one) among visitors was successful. Finding someone “there”, visiting the museum from a far away place, was an exciting experience: both if the meeting was “prearranged” or it happened by chance. The virtual museum, instead, by itself, was not very attractive to the users. One important highlight from the data we collected at the time, was that when there were no collaboration activities within the system (no other users, or nobody playing Leonardo in the virtual environment), the connection time of the users was very low (typically below five minutes). On the contrary, when forms of collaborations were enacted, users remained connected an average of 53 minutes, even engaged on a single topic.

Figure 10 - Collaboration in virtual learning environments could sustain students' attention on a single topic for one hour in average.

We had therefore the evidence that collaboration within virtual environments had a clear, outstanding and unexploited potential for attracting attention and interest of a vast range of participants, regardless of their level of education, sustaining their attention for a long time.

The architecture of Virtual Leonardo: WebTalk I

WebTalk-I was a client/server framework entirely written in Java, under the Living Worlds paradigm²¹, that allowed to easily turn VRML worlds in cooperative environments. While the server was mainly a Java application which was appointed to listen to client connections and distributing events between the participants, maintaining a centralized state repository, the client side was

composed by a Java applet which ran embedded together with a VRML window inside a regular internet browser such as Netscape or Explorer. Chances were that the average surfer already had Netscape/Explorer, with Java and the VRML browser, installed on the system. When a user hit a WebTalk HTML page in the Internet, the Java applet and the VRML embed were loaded. The VRML portion loaded the 3D geometries, while the Java applet, via the External Authoring Interface (EAI), detected events generated in the VRML worlds, and forwarded them, with the WebTalk Event Protocol, to the Server, using a TCP connection. Likewise, every other event generated in the same moment from other clients connected to the same webpage, were distributed by the central server to the Java applet on clientside, which passed them up the stack into the VRML worlds. Users could thus see each other's *avatars* (human-shaped figurines which mark every user's position), and could see objects moving and operating in response to the manipulation of other users. The use of the EAI required the implementation of some VRML PROTO's²², which had to be declared for every VRML object whose events was to be shared in the cooperative environments.

The technique was in general straightforward, requiring in most of the cases to replace the VRML Transform node declaration with a SharedObject node declaration. The SharedObject PROTO is a WebTalk-I implementation of the Living Worlds Shared Object specifications.

The authoring workflow under this kind of architecture was pretty straightforward:

1. The concept of the 3D application is sketched by the designer, which specified the environmental container (an outdoor setting, an architecture, a collection of rooms), and the objects – both local and shared – which had to be placed in a fixed position inside the container. The shared objects was available for cooperative manipulation, and the avatars could work on them while navigating within the 3D environmental container
2. The container and the objects were VRML geometries. They could be drawn with any off-the-shelf 3D modelling application, e.g. 3D Max, and were then exported into VRML. It is important, though, that the

designer took care about the complexity of the world, eventually making manual corrections to the automatically generated VRML source in order to have some degree of optimization. This is necessary to ensure lesser download time from the web and to have a lighter environment which can be drawn quicker within the Cosmo window.

3. The VRML source code was then hacked by a WebTalk-I programmer, which converts the object nodes in Shared Objects nodes, using the appropriate WebTalk-I PROTOs. To every object it was possible to attach a shared VRML sensor behavior, so it was possible to assign to an object a shared ability for translation or rotation, or a shared proximity sensibility. The effects linked to triggering of these actions can be the starting of an animation, or the opening of an HTML web page related to the object itself.
4. Once the VRML code was revised and hacked, it could be published into the HTML page which embeds the Java client and the VRML plugin. The server would serve the events of this world, which would become fully cooperative.

Cooperation within 3D environments has to be regulated by a defined set of rules. We call these rules cooperative metaphors, as they try to represent cooperation patterns of real life or try to implement new way of cooperation, which are made possible by the use of virtual reality.

In WebTalk-I the set of cooperative patterns was quite simple:

- **Global cooperation:** Under this scheme, the users enter the global environment and can chat freely with all other users.
- **Group:** The users can freely form groups. Only the participants of the same group can talk to each other.
- **Guided tour:** One participant of a group can take the special property of guidanship. All other group participants can shift their subjective vision of the 3D worlds to the vision of the guidanship owner. In this way it is possible to form virtual guided tours, with the guide taking the lead of the group, and the others that can look 'through the eyes of

the guide' when there is something worthwhile to examine in the world.

Limitation of WebTalk I

The WebTalk-I platform has proven itself useful for studying the cooperation patterns of small groups within a 3D environment.

Moreover, its web-accessibility has been proven on field, and many users did not have particular problems in bringing up the system with their home computers. However, the use of this platform for deploying 3D cooperative applications has stressed some limitations of the system, which stem out from the software components themselves, and from the architectural design of the whole system.

1. *Bottlenecks and Saturation level.* Critical bottlenecks are present both serverside and clientside²³. The main reason of the serverside bottleneck is that it takes charge of distributing all class of events (avatar movements, objects updates, world state updates, chat messages, and so forth) with the same protocol, via TCP unicasting. Moreover, this centralized scheme does not scale well over a WAN. On clientside, the bottleneck is mainly caused by the performance of standardized components. To name just an example, the EAI advise method can eat up quite some time in declaring the shared objects to be tracked within the world, and the more complex the world, the more complicated things become. The VRML browser performance (e.g. Cosmo Player) is sometimes not enough to keep track of all avatar movements within the world. This also calls for a better filtering mechanism serverside, for example with interest management. The server should send to each client only the very packets which are absolutely necessary to each client, discarding those events which will not show up on the user visualisation because of occlusions, for example. These bottlenecks and the centralized architecture bring the saturation threshold of the system to a low ten-twenty users, which is not an acceptable figure for a medium scale Net-VE.

2. *Lack of authoring flexibility.* Right now the authoring workflow, that is the procedure the designer has to follow to deploy his 3D application with the WebTalk-I framework, is not flexible enough. Geometries are to be defined once for all in VRML, and the objects are to be placed in fixed positions within the world. Subsequently a VRML programmer has to manually add the SharedObject nodes where necessary. There are two main flaws in this approach: it is difficult to update the world environment with new objects, new environment portions, new features, and the technology is not enough separated from the authoring contents: they intermix in the phase of VRML code hacking. A better solution would be to allow the creation of a repository of objects and environment parts, which can be taken and assembled at will, to form different applications even starting from the same geometry components.
3. *Lack of expressiveness.* Because of its tight link with the VRML, the expressiveness of the system is limited to the available sensors, and therefore the objects respond to interaction in terms of rotations, plane translations, proximity, and so forth. Moreover, they are stateless, they do not contain information themselves, and they are unable to react differently given different environment conditions and different inputs. In one word, they lack an internal programming logic which could turn the world's response to user interactions much more variable and intriguing. Moreover, the cooperative metaphors devised in WebTalk-I are predefined and quite limited. It would be interesting if the designer himself could design the cooperation patterns under which his world is to be explored.
4. *Software Instability and standards turbulence.* The extensive use of third-party software components, such as the EAI, the browser (Netscape or Explorer), and above all the VRML plug-in, made the system rely heavily on the general stability of this components. It happens though that none of these components is famous for its sturdiness or stability. Many of the software problems of the system come from 'layered bugs' caused by the layered architecture of WebTalk-I. These intrinsic instabilities cannot be solved but replacing the component with another one more reliable.

Another issue was the heavy turbulence of Web 3D standards at that moment. While VRML seemed to have got hold of a certain predominance, new standards were coming out, but it was uncertain if they would get spread or not. Therefore, tying the architecture to a predefined geometry format might not be a winning choice in the long term.

2.2.2 SEE – Educational Experience : WebTalkCube

The experience with “*Virtual Leonardo*” brought the team of Polytechnics of Milan to move toward an **educational environment**: the idea was to exploit the potentiality for collaboration (among students now) at the maximum extent.

The occasion came with **SEE**, *Shrine Educational Experience*²⁴, developed in partnership with the Israel Museum in Jerusalem. SEE is about the cultural, religious and historical issues related to the Dead Sea Scrolls, found in the Qumran (near the Dead Sea), in Israel. The scrolls are documents that either represent a very ancient (often the most ancient) copy of a book of the Bible, or describe features of the life and belief of this sect, living near that Dead Sea, roughly from the II century B.C. to the first century A.D.. Target for the educational collaborative experience were students of junior and senior high-schools.

The approach we were required to follow was to leverage the potential of 3D learning environments to create a new methodology of learning, based on cooperation, competition, sharing of knowledge between pairs, and interaction.

Prior to use the 3D learning environment and meet other classes in the virtual space, each class was required to prepare specific topics with the assistance of their teachers. Then the students connected to the system and started working with other classes, using the computer laboratories of their schools, and thus collaborating also with each other, “at their side” of the connection.

We have asked the teachers who took part in the experimental phase of SEE (called the “SEE Experience”), to tell us what happened in their schools. They reported about the way activities were organized, how students reacted to the project, and what in their opinion were the problems and the main educational effects of the experiment.

In order to build an effective and reliable environment, the developing team, decided to rely upon “industrialized building blocks” and the preference, was for **Macromedia Flash**, **Shockwave** and **Director**²⁵. The choice was mainly determined by the need of having a reliable technology provider (after a few “bruising experiences” with VRML engines coming in and out of the market) and a wide availability (with no additional cost for the users). The resulting environment was named **WebTalk3** (*WebTalkCube*). The 3D world was based upon the 3D

model generated by one of the commercial 3d design tool such as Discreet 3D, Studio Max, Lightwave 3d etc..

Figure 11 - SEE : in partnership with the Israel Museum in Jerusalem.

Once the 3D model was complete, it was exported (as a monolithic entity that was not possible to split into modules), in Shockwave 3D (W3D), a file format, suitable to be understood by Macromedia applications. The programmer had to import everything into the Director's stage, and only then all the dynamic aspects (including "behaviors" of the interactive objects, the events to which react, etc.) could be hard coded. Even changing position to one object or a color change, forced the programmer to ask the designer to make the changes then re-export the geometries, problems similar to the ones we already had in WebTalk-1. Furthermore the development process (including the fact that the "names" within the two environment, the modeling one and Director, had to be exactly the same) was cumbersome, confusing and expensive (e.g. Director the programmers had to learn 3D Studio Max).

Despite these problems, SEE, and its underlying software system WebTalk3, were successfully deployed and in two years more than 70 schools of 4 different countries, involving nearly 1,500 students, have used the environment for highly rewarding educational activities.

The technical problems below described required a different approach:

- *Lack of flexibility*: there was no modularization of content or behavior; everything had to be hard coded, within Director stages (using cast objects coordinated with Lingo); it was long and expensive to carry on any modification.
- *Non optimal performances*: the communication server (Macromedia Multiuser Server) worked only as “stupid” message dispatcher. Every client, which needed to communicate with another client, had to send data to this central server that forwarded it to every other client (even the ones not interested to the message). It was the job of every client to understand if to keep or to discard messages received by the server. This approach resulted in a too low refresh rate (position vectors refreshed every 2 seconds) of the shared state scene; avatars were often visualized as not moving continuously, but disappearing here and reappearing there.
- *Non optimal reliability*: as the MUS (Multi User Server) didn’t provide any acknowledgment of a received message, there was no assurance that sent messages really arrived to the server and from there to each client application. This negatively affected the overall consistency: avatars may have different positions for different clients; sometimes actions performed on a client weren’t executed at all on another client; even the chat (always served by MUS) sometimes hanged up.

2.3 General considerations and new requirements

After the successful deployment of SEE, it was decided the launch a new stream of educational applications, based on a common idea, but also with significant differences (in terms of world geometries, interactive objects, textures, collaboration features, etc.). Even within each application different versions were needed (e.g. selecting different content and different quiz for different groups of schools). **Flexibility** and **configurability** became, therefore, a crucial requirement. Moreover, in order to expand the number of schools, we needed to improve both **performances** and **reliability**, decreasing, if possibly, requirements on connection bandwidth. A number of key decisions were therefore taken for the future developments:

- Choice of a new supporting platform as **Macromedia Studio 2004 MX**: the large availability of the Macromedia Shockwave player (counting over 200 million installations all over the world) and its “industry reliability” were crucial elements. Some technical features were also relevant: e.g. the capability of importing 3D Studio file format, the support of **Havok** physics engine²⁶ (able to control and assign physics to both unanimated and animated objects and control their kinematics), the presence of a set of built in behaviors to control, for example, avatar movements.
- Use of **XML** as a configuration language: the possibility of “describing” static features (e.g. representing position, color, dimension etc. of the objects at start-up) and a dynamic features (e.g. defining if objects can be moved, clicked etc.), instead of “hard coding” them, was essential for gaining configurability and flexibility.
- Creation of a **specialized parser** to “read” the configuration file: commands, written in an Xpath like syntax, are used, in order to find attributes and metadata stored in the (XML) configuration file.

3 The WebTalk04 Framework

In this chapter we will the starting considerations for the design of the WT04 Frameworks, we'll show some related approaches to similar environments and finally we'll analyze in detail the proposed architecture

3.1 Introduction

The availability of 3D technologies on consumer platforms is continuously growing as result of the always improving of the 3D accelerated graphics hardware and the enhancements of the 3D software system. Moreover the widespread usage of internet as well as the improved average speed connection allows geographically distributed users to work together on specific tasks sharing large amount of data.

As result an always increasing number of web-based three dimensional applications has been developed, most of them working as virtual environments in which users are engaged in a common task sharing a virtual workspace (Collaborative Virtual Environments).

As said, a CVE is a computer-based, distributed, 3D virtual space or set of places that support collaborative work and social play. In such places, people, provided with graphical embodiments called avatars that convey their identity, presence, location, can meet and interact with others, with agents, or with virtual objects.

Even though CVE are increasingly becoming more and more widespread as well as the 3D technologies and design tool are, the development of collaborative three-dimensional applications seems to be deeply dependant on hard coding techniques yet too closely connected to specific web-3D formats often well suited only for particular application domains.

In our survey of the different implementations of existing commercial and academic CVE, we realized that only few of them addressed properly the major issues in developing and deploying their Collaborative VE platforms.

Our main considerations were:

- Almost all of them were **applications**, rather than **flexible frameworks**: they required extensive reprogramming for being used in different situations and for different purposes, being also inherently oriented towards code construction in a code-centered fashion. We wanted, instead, to create a “format” that could be used over and over, designing our application in a declarative way using simple authoring tools, thus using a document-

centered approach since the environment can be automatically generated from this declarative descriptions.

- The **authoring tools** they provide are often limited to each particular web-3D format. So most of 3D scenes generated are mostly monolithic and restricted with regard to both content and programming code reuse. Furthermore poor or no support was give to the **collaborative behavior design** and the **interaction control** as mean to stimulate certain kind of cooperation among users.
- They try to reach a sense of **virtual presence** as fundamental requirement through a lifelike representation of the entire rendered scene, despite of really make the whole interactive session **simply configurable** in order to allow non expert users to easily define, besides the world and avatar's appearance, also collaboration rules, allowed interactions and, more generally, to delineate how the actions can take place through the composition of action and events to arouse the sense of virtual.

3.2 Related approaches

In the following section we will describe some relevant CVE research projects proposing alternative approaches to allow and control collaborative interactions and behavior composition.

DIVE project²⁷ proposes a framework to develop multi-user interactive virtual environments. In DIVE project the programming architecture is shared, distributed world database separating application and network interface and providing a scalable system to support different users on heterogeneous networks.

MASSIVE-3 System²⁸, third edition of original **HIVE project**, is a CVE architecture based on a distributed database model making application behaviors explicitly visible within the Database. Each distributed database describes one well-defined portion of a virtual world. This system also support hierarchically structured virtual objects and heterogeneous computers and networks.

In literature there are also different approaches and solutions to combine 3D graphics and component technology. 3D component approaches²⁹ can be divided into *code-centered* and *document-centered* solutions. The code-centered view uses

component technologies oriented towards code construction using imperative programming languages. The document-centered view is based on automatically code generation from *declarative* descriptions. An example of code-centered solution is the **NSPNET-V architecture**³⁰ and **NSPNET Bamboo component system**³¹ where code modules operate in a cross-platform and cross-language manner. In this platform XML is used as a message interchange format and the components can be dynamically loaded at runtime. On the other hand **CONTIGRA project**³² define a *declarative* component architecture based on *X3D*³³ designed for the construction of Web-enable, desktop Virtual Reality applications and 3D scenes through declarative approach.

X3D supports basic 3D graphics primitives , animations, networking utilities and user interactions to define behaviors, script and communication mechanisms oriented to technical programmers not easily usable for designers and non-expert users.

The same research group proposes a concept for declaratively modeling 3D object behaviors based on X3D (*Behavior3D*³⁴).

Behavior term is, in VR system, an important concept describing interaction rules and the system state evolution. Roehl³⁵ give a definition of behavior and entity defining the first as a collection of attributes and the second as ever-changing state of all those attributes. The behaviors can be distinguished in four levels. Level 0 defines direct modification of an entity's attributes; Level 1 defines changes in an entity's attributes over time; Level 2 refers to series of calls to level 1 behaviors to perform some task and Level 3 comprises top-level decision making (level 2 behavior's selection). The behavior concept used in this chapter is quite different from the Rohel's guide lines. Our summary behavior definition is the rules derived from association between entities (object and avatars), event and action referred to geometry appearing in the virtual environment

3.3 Motivations

The research projects for which, at first time, we were asked to build a networked virtual environment have a common feature: there is an overall educational “experience” (consisting in temporally separated cooperative sessions), within which 3D worlds play a well-defined role. In the virtual environment users (mostly undergraduate students) “meet” the other users, play with them, discuss with them (via chat), in a single word they interact. The whole experience is thought as real educational course, where, in each session, 8 students (from 4 different school classes) access the 3D world simultaneously and, with the help of a *guide*, walk through the different stage of the virtual world answering cultural questions, discovering clues about some specific topics and playing interactive games.

As extensively detailed in section 2.2.2, the idea to exploit the potentiality for collaboration at the maximum extent led, at the beginning, to the design and deployment of SEE, Shrine Educational Experience, developed in partnership with the Israel Museum in Jerusalem. The whole *WebTalkCube* (that was a previous and early version of the current WebTalk04 system) architecture, used in SEE project, was based on the 3D models generated by one of the commercial 3D design tool such as Discreet 3D, Studio Max, Lightwave 3D and coded in Macromedia Flash, Shockwave and Director. The choice of the programming environment was mainly determined by the need of having a reliable web technology provider and a wide availability (with no additional cost for the users).

Main disadvantage of WebTalkCube project was that authoring and software development processes were too deeply coupled: once the 3D designer developed all geometries and models that should compose the 3D world and the objects (as a monolithic entity that was not possible to split into modules), he had to export them in Shockwave 3D (W3D), a file format, suitable to be understood by Macromedia applications. The programmer, then, had to import (at design time) everything into the Director’s stage, and only then all behaviors (of the interactive objects), the events to which react and all the dynamic aspects could be hard coded. Even changing position or color to one object, forced the programmer

to ask the designer to make the changes then re-export the geometries that at the end should be re-imported inside Director's stage. Moreover the programmer, during the software development phase, had to refer to the geometric models with the name assigned in the 3D design tool, thus making necessary a continuous interaction between him and the 3D designer. Furthermore this development process made necessary, for the programmers, to learn 3D Studio Max, with waste of time, additional costs and a little confusion about the competences required to the different actors.

This **time expensive** and **deeply involved development process** forced us to reduce at the minimum all changes and fine tuning improvements that was need during the testing and even if a little bit of user personalization was made (avatar's name, html static links, etc.) it was always to tricky to be really effective.

Learning@Europe, the next academic research project in which we were involved, was sponsored by *Accenture Foundations* (as part of the Accenture Corporate Citizenship investment program) and executed in cooperation with *Fondazione Italiana Accenture*; it was aimed at European high school students dealing with European history.

Because of the overall high number of participants expected (in the first test phase of the project more than 1000 students, from 6 different European countries, took part to the experience) and above all because of the need to personalize each session's contents (such as images, movies, questions, objects) and interaction rules (i.e. the ability to chat to each other or the move some object) depending on specific users participating and the particular topic given to the session we had to devise a different more flexible approach to the generation of collaborative 3D environments which could grant:

- a greater **easiness of configuration** both of the virtual environment settings and the collaboration issues
- a **faster session prototype process** also taking into account that, though a lot of session is very similar, sharing the main common features, there are however a lot differences due especially the different citizenship of the users thus causing: different skins of the avatars, different images of the place

they are from to be loaded in their virtual dome, different clues hidden in the virtual world, different question to answer.

On the ground of previous considerations, then the main goals of **WebTalk04** (*WT04*) architecture were:

- to provide a **flexible** and **highly decoupled development environment** to allow different developer teams to design and deploy specific 3D collaborative environments dealing with only the specific task (3D design, contents assembling, story board design, software develop) they are expert in, without regarding any other task.
- to allow to **easily define and set up sessions' prototype**, meant as set of linked 3D stages that works as a mere place where the action take place sharing the same kind of virtual experience (be it educational, entertaining, informative..), main collaboration features and the same environmental containers, from which derive different , context specific instances of virtual world, well suited for different users and situations.
- to **convey these virtual environment a high sense of virtual presence**, leaving the full graphic driven paradigm to switch towards a new one that takes the overall application design into account and to provide a set of interaction features to drive the collaboration among users in the specific way the designer was intended to do.

In my thesis we propose a **declarative format** to reduce programming need for non expert designer of the collaborative experience, for this reason we'll examine the major issues concerned in the formal description of a CVE both from a static point of view, regarding on how the virtual word is when it is generated, and from a dynamic point of view regarding on how it can evolve during the collaborative session through a declarative description of the *Event Conditioned Actions* (ECA) that can be performed in the virtual environment.

3.4 XML-based implementation

In this section we will show how the WebTalk04 declarative system is implemented using a markup language coded with XML Schema³⁶.

Figure 12 - WebTalk04 technical architecture

Since a homogeneous encoding is provided on all levels, this is a consistent approach for all abstraction stages starting from scene graph level up the description of the complex user's interactions.

Moreover an XML representation is well suited to describe the 3D scene as structured data, that can be processed without paying attention to how the data should be presented. The conversion stylesheets in fact allow the switch from one format to another. Through different **XSL files**, the content of a WT04 XML **scene graph** file could be easily converted to VRML or X3D, to pretty-printed HTML, or to any number of other formats.

Expression of scenes in XML enables application of a wide range of existing and emerging XML-based tool for transformation, translation, and processing. XML provides numerous benefits for extensibility and componentization, as well as the ability to develop well-formed and validated scene graph, an extremely valuable constraint since “broken” 3D content would no longer be allowed to escape onto the Web where it might cause larger scenes to fail.

Finally a formal XML description of the scene graph and the user-to-user or user-to-object interactions seems the best “interface” between the WT04 the following to subsystems represented within the whole architecture in Figure 12 :

- *WT04 runtime environment*, in which this XML file works as a declarative description of how the virtual world have to be rendered as well as of in which way the action can take place and evolve.
- *WT04 authoring environment* where the designer define and fine tune the world structure and the specific behaviors attached to each user or interactive objects.

As shown in Figure 13 , we devised our logical architecture as a 3 tier system detailed as follows:

Figure 13 - WebTalk04 declarative system levels

1. *Scene graph and behavior schema*: coded through XML-Schema it represents the structure of a valid WT04 compliant XML-instance, where it has been defined the elements composing XML-instances, hierarchical rules between elements and supported data types.
2. *Scene graph and behavior instance prototype*: a XML document representing the skeleton of a collaborative session where designer had already fixed geometries forming the virtual environment as well as the main users' interaction rules.
3. *Scene graph and behavior instance*: the final and XML instance completed with all information and contents depending on the specific context (specific users involved, specific target of the experience, particular topics given).

When an XML *instance* is generated, system is ready to start a collaborative session. The XML file is sent (at run time) to the clients' runtime environment (coded in Macromedia Director and Flash technology) that interprets the declarations and provides to instance the right components taken from a library (from one hand it instances the right 3D models in the world, on the other it sets up the collaboration's rule that will govern the shared experience).

3.5 Design considerations

One of the essential goals of CVE is to provide the capability of combining multi-participants and the information that they access and manipulate in a single

place. We focus our designing considerations and research work on the following components of a CVE system:

1. Virtual world representation
2. Avatars
3. Shared objects
4. Virtual actions
5. Access control and behaviors
6. Collaborative metaphors
7. Network communications

To implement an effective CVE system, we have to take care of the previous components, each playing a basic and important role in the overall system, then our declarative description we have to formally describe all these issues.

3.5.1 Virtual world representation

First of all, a CVE system has to provide a shared environment for users to cooperate with each other that we call environmental container. Then we had to design a XML based language basically to describe the 3D scene. This language uses the scene graph paradigm: a hierarchical decomposition of the renderable components in a scene.

Understanding Scene Graphs

Scene graphs are data structures used to hierarchically organize and manage the contents of spatially oriented scene data. Traditionally considered a high-level data management facility for 3D content, scene graphs are becoming popular as general-purpose mechanisms for managing a variety of media types. MPEG-4, for instance, uses the Virtual Reality Modeling Language (VRML) scene graph programming model for multimedia scene composition, regardless of whether 3D data is part of such content.

Scene Composition and Management

Scene graphs address problems that generally arise in scene composition and management. Popularized by SGI Open Inventor (the basis for VRML), scene graph programming shields you from the gory details of rendering, letting you focus on what to render rather than how to render it.

Figure 14 - Scene graph programming models shield you from underlying graphics APIs and graphics rendering and display devices.

As Figure 14 illustrates, scene graphs offer a high-level alternative to low-level graphics rendering APIs such as OpenGL and Direct3D. In turn, they provide an abstraction layer to graphics subsystems responsible for processing, eventually presenting scene data to users via monitors, stereoscopic goggles/glasses, projectors, and the like.

Before scene graph programming models, we usually represented scene data and behavior procedurally. Consequently, code that defined the scene was often interspersed with code that defined the procedures that operated on it. The result was complex and inflexible code that was difficult to create, modify, and maintain problems that scene graphs help resolve.

By separating the scene from the operations performed on it, the scene graph programming model establishes a clean boundary between scene representation and rendering. Thus, scenes can be composed and maintained independent of routines that operate on them. In addition to making things easier, this lets you create sophisticated content using visual authoring tools without regard for how that content is processed.

```
#VRML V2.0 utf8
Group {
  children [
    Shape {
```

```
geometry Sphere {}
appearance Appearance {material Material{}}
}
DEF TOUCH TouchSensor { } # define sensor
DEF LIGHT DirectionalLight { # define light
  color 1 1 0 # R G B
  on FALSE # start with light off
} ]
ROUTE TOUCH.isOver TO LIGHT.set_on
}
```

Listing 1 – sample of VRML coded scene graph

Listing 1 is VRML code for a scene consisting of a sphere that, when touched, appears yellow. As you can see, the objects and their behavior are represented at a high level. You don't know (or care) how the sphere is rendered just that it is. Nor do you know or care device is handled by the underlying run-time system to support the "touch" behavior. Ditto for the light.

At the scene level, you concern yourself with what's in the scene and any associated behavior or interaction among objects therein. Underlying implementation and rendering details are abstracted out of the scene graph programming model. In this case, you can assume that your VRML browser plugin handles low-level concerns.

Nodes and Arcs

As Figure 15 depicts, scene graphs consist of nodes (that represent objects in a scene) connected by arcs (edges that define relationships between nodes). Together, nodes and arcs produce a graph structure that organizes a collection of objects hierarchically, according to their spatial position in a scene.

Figure 15 - Scene graphs consist of nodes connected by arcs that define node relationships

With the exception of the topmost root node (which defines the entry point into the scene graph), every node in a scene has a parent. Nodes containing other nodes are parent nodes, while the nodes they contain are the child nodes (children) of their parent. Nodes that can contain children are grouping nodes; those that cannot are leaf nodes. Subgraph structures let a specific grouping of nodes exist as a discrete and independently addressed unit of data within the main scene graph structure. Operations on the scene can be performed on all nodes in the graph, or they may be restricted to a particular subgraph (scenes can therefore be composed of individual nodes as well as entire subgraphs that may be attached or detached as needed).

Scene graphs resemble tree data structures when depicted visually. Not surprisingly, trees are often used for scene graph programming. The directed acyclic graph (DAG) data structure (also known as an "oriented acyclic graph") is commonly used because it supports node sharing at a high level in the graph. Nodes in a DAG can have more than one parent, although typically at the expense of additional code complexity. In a DAG, all nodes in the graph have a directed parent-child relationship in which no cycles are allowed — nodes cannot be their own parent.

Graph Traversal

Scene graph nodes represent objects in a scene. Scene graphs used for 3D content, for instance, usually support nodes that represent 3D geometric primitives (predefined boxes, cones, spheres, and so forth), arbitrarily complex polygonal shapes, lights, materials, audio, and more. On the other hand, scene graph programming models for other forms of media might support nodes for audio/video content, timing and synchronization, layers, media control, special effects, and other functionality for composing multimedia.

Scene graph programming models support a variety of operations through traversals of the graph data structure that typically begin with the root node (root nodes are usually the entry point for scene rendering traversals). Graph traversals are required for a number of operations, including rendering activities related to transformations, clipping and culling (preventing objects that fall outside of the user's view from being rendered), lighting, and interaction operations such as collision detection and picking.

Nodes affected by a given operation are visited during a corresponding traversal. Upon visitation, a node's internal state may be set or altered (if supported) so that it reflects the state of the operation at that point in time. Rendering traversals occur almost constantly with interactive and animated graphics because the state of affairs changes as often as the user's viewpoint, necessitating continual scene graph queries and updates in response to an ever-changing perspective. To increase performance, effect caching can be used so that commonly applied operations use cached results when possible.

WT04 Scene Graph

The WT04 scene graph is organized as a sequence of 3D environments called *parts* in which users can navigate moving from one to another simply colliding to special interactive objects, often in form of ports or gate, working as teleports thus causing the unloading of the current part rendered by the engine and the loading the next one.

Figure 16 - Top level scene graph XML Schema

Since this environmental container can be considered a mere sort of stage where the action can take place, we can think at it as a whole, monolithic composite geometry without any kind of interactivity or behavior.

On the basis of this consideration we described the stage in the XML through a single model entry as follows:

```
<World>
  +<Configuration>
  +<Part num="1" url="@/Part/MeetingPoint.W3D" descr="First stage">
  +<Part num="2" url="@/Part/TreasureHunt.W3D" descr="Second stage">
</World>
```

Listing 2 - Sample of WT04 scene graph coded in its XML schema

It's clear that new world instance can be generated simply by putting together and reusing different parts already configured thus creating new virtual sessions as composition of pre-existent modules.

3.5.2 Avatars

Avatars are graphical embodiments representing the participants in the collaborative virtual experience. WT04 schema describes avatars using a particular node structure with the following features:

1. Avatar Identification Properties

These properties describe how the particular avatar looks like. We can set up, for example, the avatar's skin, the avatar's vest (that be due to the team membership), and the avatar's trousers. In this way, we can set up a particular avatar's figure that is recognizable by others in the virtual world.

2. Relative Position and Orientation

With this set of properties we are able to fine set up the start position, orientation and scale of each avatar at the beginning of a each session. So we can specify all the geometric variables that allows to instance a particular avatar in a particular position (and particular geometrical peculiarity such as scale and orientation) during the scene set up at start time.

3. *Character Control Parameters*

This set of properties to change avatar’s physics parameters (mostly affecting its movements). Here we can set up the avatars walk speed, the run speed and his mass.

4. *Animation Control Parameters*

This parameters control the avatar’s animations properties. This properties are used to initialize the module that govern avatar’s animation.

Figure 17 - Avatar node

This high flexibility and reconfiguration easiness is one of the key points to allows designers to tailor specific graphical embodiments over each user involved in the session thus emphasizing their sense of awareness of “being there”.

We can shape all the avatar’s characteristics so that users belonging to the same team (i.e. the same class), have some graphical feature in the virtual world,

defined in *Avatar Identification Properties* shown above, that visually associates them together.

On the other hand, we can use one different avatar (with different traits, skin, animations) for each distinct user by simply associating the right 3D character model from an external geometries' repository (grouped inside a component library).

3.5.3 Shared objects

WebTalk04 architecture make use of two different kind of objects: from one hand, we use object (typically embedded in the part file) that are static geometrical file used to populate the scene graph; on the other hand we use Shared Objects that are deeply dynamic objects that can interact with the other components in the collaborative session. Shared Objects are loaded and instanced at start time. WebTalk04 architecture can do mostly everything with this kind of object because we can apply all the geometrical and textures transformations. We can configure two different Shared Objects Properties:

Figure 18 - Object node

1. Static Properties

In this XML section we set up the object's geometrical configuration (*tags Geometry*), such us the world position (X, Y, Z), the rotation (rotX, rotY, rotZ), and other properties connected with the shared object's appearance.

2. Dynamic Properties

The dynamic properties (*tags Behaviors*) involves with the interplay that the specific shared object can have. Each Shared Object, in fact, interact with other objects in the world. Configuring this XML node we describe how the shared object reacts to external solicitations. In few words, we are able to fine set up all the behaviors that the shared object can have dynamically.

As seen, our modular approach based on the hierarchical representation of entities (i.e. user and objects) makes simple the process of populating the scene graph with shared objects and to assign the right behavior in a particular collaborative context.

3.5.4 Virtual actions

In WT04 architecture, all the collaboration issues are configurable by a set of action that take effect on a specific object or set of object, or generically on the collaborative shared environment. From a WebTalk04 point of view, actions are single components that are invoked in a particular instant by someone (typically an avatar) or something (typically an object). So actions are modules that we can configure in order to obtain the dynamic reaction we want.

Below are listed the most important action modules that our architecture supports (more detailed view in next sections):

- *DragObject*: Allows to drag the shared object in the 3D world. This is a 3D drag that allows to move and rotate the shared object.
- *ChangeColor* or *ChangeTexture*: Changes the color or the texture of the specified shared object.
- *Showtooltip*: Shows a label near the object in the 3D world.
- *StarTrek*: Moves the avatar in a specific part.
- *goToUrl*: Opens a new browser window on a specific page. This is used to open boards, for example.
- *StartAnimation*: This action is used to starts shared object embedded animation.

3.5.5 Access control and behaviors

In WebTalk04 the collaboration issues between user-to-user or user-to-object is intrinsically correlated to interactions' primitives above mentioned as virtual actions supported by the environment as well as its capability to control and drive collaboration in a specific and well defined direction.

In this sense issues as object ownership and resource management have a great importance on the whole architecture.

Access control is a familiar concept in such field as operating systems and Computer Supported Collaborative Workgroups (CSCW)³⁷. The term '**access model**' refers to a set of mechanisms used by a system to determine the operations that may be carried out on a given object by a given user.

In a CVE we need a set of rules or access patterns which determine whether a user, group of users, or user playing a particular role, can perform a specified action.

As our main concern is to control and drive collaboration through appropriate policy of resource and interaction control, we can divide, according to the resource access in Virtual Environments systems in two main types:

1. **Class based access.** Is a programmatic and developer issue and is concerned above all with the integrity and the structure of the underlying programs/objects that form the VE.
2. **Object based access.** Refers to the relationship between the affordances of objects and their users as, for example, the availability of an object to be "moved" or "owned" in some way. This is the type of access paradigm on which we founded WT04 interaction model and its runtime engine.

In our model, interaction is achieved and controlled through a mechanism based on three main concepts using the paradigm of *Event Conditioned Actions*:

- **Entity:** a general resource within the system. An entity may be a shared object with a graphical representation, or an abstract concept with no visible representation as, for example, a server side remote shared object mapping a certain property of the system. Such entities provide a set properties representing in some way the inner state of the entity and an

amount of listener which the entity is registered to that allow to react events and perform one or more actions. In this view users and their own avatars can be considered a particular kind of entity.

- **Event:** is a trigger that can be raised by some users' interaction or by the system itself, notifying that some thing has happened in the shared environment. Events can be grouped in three main types depending on the different kind of interaction by which they are caused:
 - *Indirect active events:* they are active since it's the user himself to raise the event , but indirect as they are not generated by a direct voluntary user's action such as a mouse click on some entity but it's the system to raise them reacting for example to a particular user's position. A typical example of such event is *OnProximity* , raised whenever an entity is closer to another one than a fixed value.
 - *Direct active events:* in this case it's the user voluntarily to raise the event interacting directly with an entity
 - *Passive events:* they are generated by a shared system state change (i.e. position update event for some entity)
- **Action:** see par. 3.5.4 Virtual actions .

According to the classical view the Event Conditioned Actions' rules are based on the following form:

on event
if conditions
do actions

Moreover in our declarative model the central concepts around which all the scene graph is described are the *objects* and *users*, or, in more general worlds, *entities*.

Then we derived the following entity-oriented interaction control model:

Figure 19 - Interaction control model

In this model the main component is entity that can be thought as an abstraction of both users, as active actors of the system allowed to raise events, and objects, as passive components of the system which listens to events propagated within the virtual environment and reacts to them performing one or more actions.

Action target can be indifferently the same entity which caused in some way the event, or another different one.

The group made of Event and Action take the name of *Behavior* as states the manner in which some entity evolve the system state when perturbed.

Using this model we can design and code different behavioral situations; for example the following pseudo code:

```

on event. MouseLeftClick
if (event.clickedobject.name="cube01" and
    event.clickedobject.distance<800)
do cube01.changeColor(#red)
  
```

would be translated in declarative form in:

```

<Object Name="Cube01">
  <Geometry>
    <Location URL="@/object/board11.W3D"
ModelResource="board11"/>
    <Appearance URL=""/>
    <Position X="-2112.408" Y="577.9936" Z="160.6084"/>
    <Rotation X="90" Y="0" Z="-180"/>
    <Scale X="2" Y="2" Z="2"/>
  
```

```
</Geometry>
<Behaviour>
  <OnClick Far="800">
    <Action Type="ChangeColor" Property="#red"/>
  </OnClick>
</Behaviour>
</Object>
```

Listing 3 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing a generic behaviour attached to an interactive object

which states at the same time:

- the way how the object should be represented in the CVE, through the `<Geometry>` element
- the way how it reacts to events in one word how it behaves, through the element `<Behaviour>`

As the structured XML elements representing the entities' appearance and behavior make use of intuitive concepts and of a human readable form, we can confident that even non programmers without programming skills or any knowledge of scripting languages can understand, manage and produce valid XML world instance that will configure the runtime environment producing the 3D representation and the interactions expected.

Moreover the XML code and component reuse reduce the time to create a particular experience instance, abates the error's rate, allowing to verify in real time every change made on the setup of the virtual environment.

3.5.6 Collaborative metaphors

Collaborative Metaphors³⁸ are set of rules to support interaction and collaboration between users who want to explore complex content and information together. The rules determines how the “collaborative community” can be created and managed, how every member of the community can operate on his/her own or can cooperate with other members. Different types of situation, tasks and users roles determine different behaviors and therefore need different

metaphors. WebTalk04 architecture offers a huge support to collaborative metaphors. We can set up in the XML world configuration file a set of specific behaviors that can be applied to a specific metaphor. So we can select what behavior is applied to a specific shared object in a particular moment. When the specific collaborative metaphor is activated, the corresponding set of interaction rules take effect, and every object uses the right behavior to interact with the “shared world”. There are two different way to activate a metaphor:

1. *Explicit way*: it can be started manually (and asynchronously) by a power user.
2. *Implicit way*: an interaction in the virtual shared world generates a “Change Metaphor Sync Message” that tells all the clients to switch the active metaphor to the new one. All the clients update the new set of rules that are effective.

As seen above, thanks to the Collaborative Metaphor paradigm, we are able to manage complex interactions between entities in a virtual shared environment, specifying the current set of collaboration’s rules governing every aspect of the virtual world.

Let’s see now, how we can translate a complex interaction rule in an XML based description used by WebTalk04 engine to control the mutual interplays generated in/by the shared world.

Let’s suppose we want to map this interaction rule:

“When user Garibaldi is close to the gate, the object named ‘cube01’ change its color to green on all the connected user’s clients, and all the users are moved to the part number 2. When this particular user left clicks on this object, the system opens a browser window that links to the url www.somewhere.net”

This is a set of rules that are active only when the selected (fixed) user is close to a particular object: this is what we call Collaborative Metaphor. The XML translation is:

```
<Object Name="Cube01" Physics="Yes">  
  <Geometry>  
    .....  
  </Geometry>  
  <Behaviour>
```

```
<Metaphors>
  <Metaphor num="1">
    <User name="Garibaldi">
      <OnLeftClick Far="400">
        <Action Type="GoToUrl" where="www.somewhere.net"/>
      </OnLeftClick>
      <OnProximity Distance="3000" Persistence="0">
        <Action Type="StarTrek" Property="UsST2"/>
        <Action Type="ChangeColor" Target="Cube01" Property="#green"/>
      </ OnProximity >
    </User>
  </Metaphor>
</Metaphors>
</Behaviour>
</Object>
```

Listing 4 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing the instance of a collaborative metaphor

Obviously, defining a huge number of metaphors and melting them together, we can govern the collaborative environment recreating the exact collaborative situation we wanted.

3.5.7 Network communications

This node of the WT04 XML Schema allows us to fine configure the network access. We use a simple declarative approach that permit to easily decide which communication server we have to use to share the experience state, and a set of properties that characterize the connection between the specific client and the communication server. This is a list of the most important parameters we can set up:

- *FCServer*: Communication Server IP number and the experience instance name.
- *FPSSharedUsers*: This values configures the specific avatar position's upload and download refresh rates. An high value means a more detailed position tracking (but more bandwidth is required!!).

Figure 20 - Network configuration node

As seen, we can use specific XML file in order to set up different bandwidth speed on different client machines. In this way we allow clients with dissimilar connection speeds to access together and simultaneously to the same virtual world ensuring the world share state consistence.

3.6 System architecture

The WebTalk04 project makes extensive use of Macromedia technology, while keeping the goals of web-accessibility and use of standard components.

The choice of using Macromedia is strategic because of the large spread of the Macromedia Shockwave player counting over 200 million installations all over the world and at the same time allowing the use of a solid, tested and free software player without the need of implementing another one.

The WebTalk04 system architecture is written in different programming languages: Lingo (Director coding) with all its extensions made available in recent times as Netlingo and 3D Lingo, Action Script 2 (Flash coding).

The architecture is deeply based over a client/server paradigm and exploits an application server hosting a Web Server for static and dynamic contents and a Communication Server (Macromedia Flashcomm) for sharing data in cooperative and distributed applications.

While the server is appointed to listen to client connections and distributing events between the participants, maintaining a centralized state repository, the client side is composed by a Shockwave plug-in which runs inside a regular internet browser such as Netscape or Explorer.

Chances are that the average surfer already has Netscape/Explorer, with Shockwave plug-in installed on the system.

When a user hits a WebTalk04 HTML page in the Internet, the Shockwave player embedded are loaded, the user of a WebTalk application sees a browser window, which is split in two parts.

The upper half is a W3D movie showing the 3D representation on the world, in which the visitor can move and interact with objects . In this portion of the screen the user can also see other visitors moving and performing actions. A human-shaped figurine (avatar) represents every visitor. In the lower half of the screen a chat window is provided as flash flat panel in which visitors can write messages to other visitors, and can read incoming messages.

Figure 21 - A scene from Learning@Europe, an educational application for European schools

In order to build a general application, the W3D portion doesn't embed 3D geometries but the system builds the virtual scene in real time, fetching the separate geometries and textures from a repository; the geometries can be in any of the most common formats currently available, be it 3DS, Plasma, Maya or Lightwave.

The collaboration logic, via the WebTalk Interaction Engine (WtIE), detects every event generated both in 2D or 3D interface, and forwards them, through the Real Time Message Protocol (RTMP), to the Server. Likewise, every other event

generated in the same moment from other clients connected to the same webpage, are distributed by the Flash Communication Server to the Shockwave plug-in on client side, which passes them up the stack into the W3D worlds.

Users can thus see each other's avatars (human-shaped figurines which mark every user's position), and can see objects moving and operating in response to the manipulation of other users.

All the system architecture is built up around the MVC (Model View Controller) design pattern, in which the model represents the shared world state, the view represents each client web application, and the controller is the programming logic that builds up and regulates each end user GUI as well as the shared state.

Figure 22 - WebTalk04 general architecture

The architecture of WebTalk04 is shown in Figure 22. Let us now describe all its components:

➤ **Client side**

The “world engine” is the client-side of the application. Through a number of modules, it manages the connection with the server and controls the rendering on the client machine. The “interaction engine”, in particular, controls the collaboration features, while “world builder” renders in real time the scene, according with the shared state of all the objects and avatars.

➤ **Server Side**

- Contents Repositories: they store all the geometries and the textures, created at design time.
- XML files repository: it stores all the different configuration (XML) files. When a client starts a session, the system select the right XML file and loads it.
- Communication Server: it keeps the actual shared state, keeping track, for example, of positions, rotations, and “state” in general all the avatars and objects. Any change of the shared state is detected and send to all the clients, raising an “onSync” signal.

➤ **Back End**

It consists of a set of tools that allow the “sessions architects” to configure and fine tune all the session parameters.

In order to deploy the application, any Web server (as IIS or TomCat) can be used; the Communication Server, instead, is a dedicated server managing the interaction between each client and the server. The communication server, in particular, for each shared object maintains several versions: one “*remote shared object*” preserving the state on the communication server; many “*local shared objects*” (one for each client) being updated locally. Whenever one interactive element of a client changes one or more of its properties, its corresponding local shared object is refreshed and at the same time it notifies the communication server the updated value storing it in its remote shared object; at every “*onSync*” event generated by the communication server, each client receives, inside the OnSync message, a vector of the changes occurred since the last refresh thus updating the value of each slot of their local shared objects.

3.6.1 System Users

WetTalk04 framework provide access to several different kind of users:

- *Administrator* :
has a full power on data, can create new user profiles, modify the existing one, and, in general, check the correct working of the platform;
- *Content modeler* :

is the handler of the contents, in particular has to configure the geometries populating the virtual world (for example by correctly positioning the interactive objects in the virtual environment), moreover he has to personalize contents (avatar skin, html pages, supported behaviour) and to define the rules of the collaboration between user.

– *Scheduler* :

handle the schedule of each collaborative experiences defining the composition of the teams, the meeting date and hour etc.

– *Guide* :

is the supervisor of a collaborative experience who is allowed to access the virtual world; he has more privileges : enables generic users to enter the session, allows them to pass from an environment to another, changes the users' power (increasing for example their walk or flight speed) and finally he drives users in the discover of the 3D worlds proposing cultural based games and questions.

– *Generic user* :

is the most important stakeholder of the system, normally is a pupil registered to a collaborative experience, that has to compete, with the help of his team mate, against the opposite team. He can be either a 3D user, which is represented in the virtual world by an avatar, or a 2D user that has only chat capabilities

Figure 23 - WT04 system users

3.6.2 Use case diagrams

In this section, we'll analyze the main user of WT04 system whose interaction are however representative also for other users.

Parameters change (change fixed view)

ACTOR	SYSTEM
Generic-user presses the change view key	The ShockWave applet on client-side sets the next of teh avaiable cameras.

Moves inside the 3D world

ACTOR	SYSTEM
-------	--------

Generic-user presses arrow keys	The ShockWave applet on client-side moves the avatar inside the 3D stage and sends back to Flash Communication Server the updated coordinates
---------------------------------	---

Other users detection.

ACTOR	SYSTEM
Another generic-user connects to the 3D world	The ShockWave applet on client-side, receives the notification of the new connection, clones the avatar model and register the shared object representing it.
Another generic-user moves his avatar	The ShockWave applet on client-side, receives the new coordinate set and place the avatar in the new position.
Interaction with another object.	The ShockWave applet on client-side, receives the new coordinates or the event of a new action performed, repalce the object or activates the action.
Generic-user disconnection.	The ShockWave applet on client-side, receives the notification of the disconnection, removes the avatar clone from the stage and the corresponding shared object.

Interacts with an object

ACTOR	SYSTEM
Generic-user moves an object through the mouse.	The ShockWave applet on client-side, moves the object inside the 3D world and sends new coordinates to the Flash Communication Server.
Generic-user activates an action on some object.	The ShockWave applet on client-side, activates the action and notifies the Flash Communication Server.

3.6.3 Activity Diagram

Initialization

The following diagram shows the activities related to the initialization of the 3D world on the basis of the formal description container in the XML document.

Connection/Disconnection

The following diagram shows the activities related to the connection/disconnection of the client Shockwave applet from the Flash Communication Server.

User Activities

The following diagram shows the activities related to the users' actions.

Sequence diagrams

This diagram shows the all the operations sequence from the initial connection to the application to the final disconnection.

3.6.4 Webtalk04 session lifecycle

The full understating of the general WebTalk platform is strictly linked to the comprehension of how a generic experience is designed, developed and deployed.

Figure 24 – Webtalk04 session's lifecycle

The idea about the structure and the contents characterizing the experience is the result of the work of a group of experts, the **Experience Architects** team, constituted by psychologists, pedagogues, historians, teachers, and any other experts needed by the special target of the experience has to be designed. The output of this first phase is the design of the main format of the collaborative virtual experience, the main storyboard on the basis of the specific argument has to be presented and the age and cultural level of the users that will take part to the experience.

The definition of the scenery and of the interaction rules are the inputs for two more actors, respectively the **3D World Designers** and the **Session Configurator**.

3D World Designers are expert of 3D modeling and, on the basis of the requirements given by Experience Architects, build (using for example 3D Studio Max) the main stage (the environmental container) and all the interactive objects have to be used during the collaborative meetings.

After this phase, the session designer collects all the modeled geometries and, following the interaction rules specified by Experience Architects, compiles an XML instance of the WT04 configuration file.

This is the formal description either of the 3D environment in which the actions take place or of all the possible interactions allowed there; this declarative description is then interpreted by the WebTalk Runtime Engine that renders the scene on each client application and control every user interaction.

3.6.5 Flexibility and Implementation

One of the Webtalk04 most important architectural key point is the high degree of flexibility and configurability. In fact there is an *XML World configuration* file that allows to setup every single aspect of the physical structure of collaborative environment and every collaboration issue. As it was said before, the files describes both static and dynamic features.

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<World>
  <Part num="1" url="@/Part/MeetingPoint.W3D">
    <Avatar>
      <Geometry>
        <Location URL="@/avatar/man1.W3D" ModelResource="uomo"/>
        <Position X="-1828" Y="-33" Z="180"/>
        <Rotation X="0" Y="0" Z="0"/>
        <Scale X="0.9" Y="0.9" Z="0.9"/>
        <CharacterController WalkSpeed="300" RunSpeed="700" JumpStrength="600" Mass="100000"/>
      </Geometry>
    </Avatar>
    <Object Name="Boardses11" Physics="Yes" mod="1" descr="">
      <Geometry>
        <Location URL="@/object/board11.W3D" ModelResource="board11"/>
        <Position X="-2112.408" Y="577.9936" Z="160.6084"/>
        <Rotation X="90" Y="0" Z="-180"/>
        <Scale X="2" Y="2" Z="2"/>
      </Geometry>
      <Behaviour>
        <OnLeftClick Far="400">
          <Action Type="GoToUrl" Property="@/contents/LE_exprnumexp/session/teamA.htm"/>
        </OnLeftClick>
        <OnMouseOver CursorType="280" Far="400">
          </OnMouseOver>
        <OnProximity Distance="3000" Persistence="0">
          <Action Type="ChangeTexture" Property="@/static_img/teamA.bmp"/>
        </OnProximity>
      </Behaviour>
    </Object>
  </Part>
</World>
```

Listing 5 - Sample piece of XML configuration

Listing 5 shows an example of configuration file: the world description is divided in <part> elements, each describing a single environment in which the

session takes place. A “part element” is characterized by its environmental container (i.e. a geometrical file that is considered as a “stage” in which we instance avatars and objects) and contains one `<avatar>` element and a list of `<object>` elements. Each object section is composed by a `<geometry>` element (describing geometry model, position, rotation ...) and a `<behavior>` element (describing the possible interaction rules).

Each avatar can interact with other avatars, as well as with the objects, through a programmable action (i.e. open a URL, change color, move to a different position) executed in reaction of the raising a specific event (i.e. object proximity, collision detection, left click ...). *MouseOver*, *MouseClicked*, *OnProximity*, *OnSync* are some of the most important events that can be used.. *OnProximity* event is raised when the distance between the user (Avatar) and the object is less than a fixed value. The *OnSync* event is raised when something is changed in the shared status of an object. When an event is raised, the engine executes the appropriate action.

```
<Object Name="Board" Physics="Yes" mod="1" descr="">
  <Geometry>
    .....
  </Geometry>
  <Behaviour>
    <OnLeftClick Far="400">
      <Action Type="GoToUrl" Property="@/contents/LE/session/teamA.htm"/>
    </OnLeftClick>
    .....
  </Behaviour>
</Object>
```

Listing 6 - Example of behavior definition

In the Listing 6 the object named *Board* reacts to a left click performed by the user with the action *GoToUrl* that opens a browser windows that links to a web page. The user perception is that by clicking on a panel (board) (s)he gets a web page.

3.6.6 Configuration and authoring tools

In order to create a different variation of a session (e.g. changing some of the behaviors, changing the ways some objects react, etc.) it is sufficient (for the designer) to update the XML file. All the clients must load the XML configuration file at the very beginning of the session. The drawback is that in complex situations, as the ones that we need to handle, when multiple worlds, several objects, several patterns of behavior are involved, the XML file can become large and complex. Generation and maintenance of XML files is must be efficient and reliable (in one of the applications where WT04 was used we had to generate 12 variations of each one of the 4 sessions, i.e. 48 different configurations).

We can define two different kind of “configuration’s issues”:

- *world configuration phase*: in which designers describe every generic environmental container and the main interaction rules. This description is common to all the collaborative sessions sharing the same “storyboard”
- *session configuration phase*: in which designers can set up additional details (e.g. avatars’ names and skin, boards’ textures ...), i.e. the variations of the basic pattern.

Two different authoring tools are therefore needed:

- *world configurator*: it generates an XML “template” with the skeleton of the 3D world from a geometrical point of view. The designer is provided with a WYSIWYG graphical interface (with preview windows and point and click tools). (S)he can describe the overall structure of the 3D world, can place objects (selecting them from a list, dragging them and dropping them in the right place), can assign to each object fixed attributes’ values (i.e. color, scale, etc.) and even the desired general interactive dynamic behaviors’ primitive (i.e. `change_color`, `open_url`, etc.), as reaction to predefined events. The preview window shows how the world looks like, in order to tune the position, and the orientation of each object with a “single click”.
- *session configurator*: it allows to select every object and assign the correct value to every behavior or object’s attribute. We can, for example, personalize a session prototype previously defined through the above world

configurator on the basis of the specific players involved and the topic given to them

The tools are (relatively) designer friendly; therefore even a “non-techy” designer can create and setup an experience. This is a very important capability, since it reduces the managerial complexity of quickly creating different variations of a same session.

3.6.7 Collaborative features

As said, we call “collaborative metaphors³⁸” a set of basic rules which describe different modalities of interaction between users and between the users with the environment. These rules encompass various aspects, such as the way users can gather in groups, the possible ways of chatting to each other, the way to navigate in the virtual space, how to visualize the world and objects, etc.. Taking decisions on all these aspects, shapes a collaborative situation; within one of our sessions (approximately lasting 50 minutes) we need to change several time the collaborative situation, moving from an initial presentation, to a discussion, to a game, etc.

Figure 25 - The Treasure Hunt in the guide’s view

Let’s analyze in detail how WT04 supports an intrinsic collaborative game such the collaborative treasure hunt.

Avatars have to look for objects hidden in a labyrinth; of course during the treasure hunt flying is forbidden (first rule), otherwise they would spot the object almost immediately! On the other hand, avatars can be forced to use some features:

an object (for example) can be selected as the only after consultation with a team mate (second rule) and, consequently, players are encouraged at looking at it through his avatar's eyes (third rule).

WebTalk04 has 2 different chat panels: one is a public chat panel in which all users can chat, another is a team whisper chat, only users of the same team can chat together. The guide can allow/disable the chat system to decide if a user can use the chat system or not (it is important to block the chat system, for example, during a lecture).

3.6.8 Performances

As in a 3D collaborative environment all the users shares the world status, all the clients should see the same "scene" at the same time. Unfortunately it is technically impossible to keep the status aligned on all clients, because clients access the architecture from places geographically distributed and with different types of connection, and therefore there is a different "traveling time" for every message going from the server to each client, and vice versa. The WT04 architecture, however, provides a solid connection manager that optimizes all the connection to overwork even the poorest bandwidth.

During a collaborative session, a player can hold a different bandwidth quota in different collaboration contexts: when he is engaged in a chat session, for example, he doesn't use much bandwidth because he has only to send simple chat text to the collaboration server; in a game context, on the contrary, he takes up lot of bandwidth to ensure a live position and rotation synchronization on all the clients connected. The state alignment is very important mostly during game and highly collaborative tasks because users can interact only if they are sure that the state of the others players is up to date. When an avatar moves in the 3d world we have to refresh his six degree of freedom sending to the server the right position and rotation ($x, y, z, rotx, roty, rotz$). Using the shared object approach we are sure that we are sending only the "slot" changed by the movement. For example if an avatar moves following straightly in one direction (i.e. parallel to x axis), we can send only the actual x position to the server. The server packs this new "slot value" and broadcasts the *OnSync* signal to all the clients listening. Another important issue is that the

global bandwidth is proportional to the number of players. If we have one more player we have to listen to more shared object and to use more bandwidth.

On the basis of the above considerations, the WT04 architecture optimizes the bandwidth usage, by refreshing with different rates clients state with different connection speeds. Table 1 shows some measurement of the bandwidth used by WT04 during real sessions and represents the real bandwidth use per client. We analyzed three different scenarios depending on the number and the kind of user connected to the 3D world.

SCENARIO	TYPICAL BEARING	Average Bandwidth Usage (KByte/sec)
Lessons and Homework presentation	8 chatting and 2 walk around 3D world	1.11
Treasure Hunt Game	2 chatting and 8 walk around 3D world	2.88
Capability and Quiz Game	4 chatting and 6 walk around 3D world	1.89

Table 1 - Average bandwidth usage measurements

Our approach allows even to clients with low speed connection to engage in a 3D cooperative experience with acceptable performances. Looking at the future, however, we can do it even better: i.e. improving bandwidth optimization working on the process of collecting the position samples (*x, y, z positions and rotation*). In current implementation, in fact, the position acquiring process works at a fixed rate. We would like to improve the bandwidth global performance creating a “smart agent” that, from one hand, controls (in real time) how much bandwidth quota is used by each client, by the other hand, defines the correct quota needed to update correctly its state. In this way, the “smart agent” determines the sampling rate founded on the actual measurement and on the global net workload. In this manner a client with a poor connection will lose some details but it will still be able to participate.

3.7 XML Language

The WebTalk04 interaction engine is based on the interaction control model described in paragraph *Access control and Behaviour*: **Events** that occur during the normal evolution of the application raise some **Actions** the modify the state of the world and determinate the interaction with the **Objects**, included the avatars representing the other users of the virtual environment.

In the below figure it's defined a standard scheme that will be used to describe the events interpreted by interaction engine and the resulting actions.

Figure 26 - Interaction control model

It's evident that there are two different kind of entities that can generate an event: a “normal” **User** of the application and a **Server Side Agent**, for example a software module that uses a server side business logic from which results depends some events in the 3D world.

3.7.1 Events

MouseOver&Click

In this section will be reviewed all events regarding the use of the mouse, such as: *OnMouseOver*, *OnLeftClick*, *OnRightClick*. These events are generated only by the user.

Below the corresponding model:

Figure 27 - MouseOver & Click events

An example of use of this events in the XML configuration code:

```

<Object Name="Boardses01" Physics="Yes" mod="1" descr="">
  <Geometry>
    <Location URL="@/object/board_S2_1.W3D" ModelResource="board_S2_1"/>
    <Appearance URL=""/>
    <Position X="969.2983" Y="-1408.298" Z="-5809.896"/>
    <Rotation X="90" Y="0" Z="34.7364"/>
    <Scale X="2" Y="2" Z="2"/>
  </Geometry>
  <Behaviour>
    <OnLeftClick>
    <Action Type="GoToUrl" Property="@/contents/ses3/world_html/board1.htm"/>
    </OnLeftClick>
    <OnMouseOver CursorType="280">
    </OnMouseOver>
  </Behaviour>
</Object>
  
```

Listing 7 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing an instance of mouse related events

In the <Behaviour> element there are two different triggers: the first reacts to the event *OnLeftClick* and the second to the event *OnMouseOver* and both generates Actions that will be described later on.

OnProximity

This event reacts to the approaching of some avatar to some interactive object, when the distance is less than the minimum defined, the event is raised.

Figure 28 - OnProximity event

An example of use of this event in the XML configuration code:

```

<Object Name="PortaGialla" Physics="Yes" mod="1" descr="">
  <Geometry>
    <Location URL="@/object/porta3.w3d" ModelResource="porta3"/>
    <Appearance URL=""/>
    <Position X="659.1268" Y="-410.2651" Z="-9.6810"/>
    <Rotation X="0" Y="0" Z="54.6787"/>
    <Scale X="0.2580" Y="0.2580" Z="0.3039"/>
  </Geometry>
  <Behaviour>
    <OnProximity Distance="10" Persistence="1" >
      <Action Type="StarTrek" Property="UsST3"/>
    </ OnProximity >
  </Behaviour>
</Object>
  
```

Listing 8 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing an instance of proximity events

Note the parameter **Distance** of the element OnProximity representing the minimum limit beyond which the event is raised; and the parameter **Persistence** that determines whether the event will be performed only once (persistence=1) or every time the conditions on distance will be verified (persistence=0).

OnSync

It is an event raised when a shared object changes some of its properties, it is the main behaviour designed to handle the interactions between client and server and it's used to activate actions on specific clients that, in some way, depend on

the happening of some server side condition. In particular, the parameters of the OnSync event are:

- the name of the remote shared object
- the value it have to assume to active the corresponding action

Figure 29 - OnSync event

An example of use of this event in the XML configuration code:

```

<Object Name="board1lab" Physics="Yes" mod="1" descr="">
  <Geometry>
    <Location URL="@/object/board_01.w3d" ModelResource="board_01"/>
    <Appearance URL=""/>
    <Position X="-239,191" Y="-377,68" Z="-1834.29"/>
    <Rotation X="90" Y="0" Z="155.89"/>
    <Scale X="1.5" Y="1.5" Z="1.5"/>
  </Geometry>
  <Behaviour>
    <OnSync NameSharedObj="textures" value="1">
      <Action Type="ChangeTexture" Property="@/contents/session2/img/frasi/fraseA.bmp"/>
    </OnSync>
  </Behaviour>
</Object>
  
```

Listing 9 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing an instance of the onSync event

3.7.2 Actions

All the *actions* supported by WT04 are coded in a lingo script called **Actions**, whenever a particular event is raised the invoked action is performed according to

its implementation in this script, so to enrich the number of supported action is sufficient to refactor only this particular software module.

Supported actions are:

- *DragObject* function let the objects be moved by avatars
- *StartAnimation* performs the animation attached to an object
- *ChangeColor* creates a new shader (a map for a color) and assigns it to the object desired
- *ChangeTexture* creates a new texture and assigns it to the object desired
- *Showtooltip* shows on the active camera, the *tooltip* behind the mouse cursor, whose text is defined in the XML configuration file, whenever the
- *StarTrek* works as a teleport making the user to disappear from a place to reappear to another
- *SendSharedObj* sends to the server the value of some property that as changed in the observed object
- *goToUrl* loads on the screen the URL passed as parameter

DragObject

DragObject is the action that allows to move any interactive object in the stage thought the mouse drag & drop.

The property parameter represents the refresh rate used to send to the server every update of the object position.

Its interaction control model is the following.

Figure 30 – DragObject action

An example of use of this action in the XML configuration code:

```
<Object Name="discorosso" Physics="Yes" mod="1" descr="">
```

```

<Geometry>
  <Location URL="@/object/discored.w3d" ModelResource="discored"/>
  <Appearance URL=""/>
  <Position X="-239,191" Y="-377,68" Z="-1834.29"/>
  <Rotation X="90" Y="0" Z="155.89"/>
  <Scale X="1.5" Y="1.5" Z="1.5"/>
</Geometry>
<Behaviour>
  <UserA1>
    <OnMouseOver CursorType="280" >
    </OnMouseOver>
    <OnLeftClick>
      <Action Type="DragObject" Property="25"/>
    </OnLeftClick>
  </UserA1>
</Behaviour>
</Object>

```

Listing 10 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing an instance of DragObject action

StartAnimation

StartAnimation performs the animation that is linked to a specified object. Its interaction control model is the following.

Figure 31 – StartAnimation action

An example of use of this action in the XML configuration code:

```

<Object Name="clessidra">
  <Behaviour>
    <OnSync NameSharedObj="textures" value="4">
      <Action Type="StartAnimation" Property="clessidra-Key"/>
    </OnSync>
  </Behaviour>
</Object>

```

```

    </Behaviour>
  </Object>

```

Listing 11 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing an instance of DragObject action

The property parameter defines the which particular animation has to be performed.

Its important to underline that any animation can be activated either from a normal user interaction through the triggers *MouseOver*, *OnProximity* or from a server call through the *OnSync* trigger.

ChangeColor

ChangeColor action assigns a new shader of the speficied color to the desired object. The events that can activate this action are : *Clicks*, *OnMouseOver*, *OnProximity*.

Its interaction control model is the following.

Figure 32 – ChangeColor action

An example of use of this action in the XML configuration code:

```

< Object Name="discorosso" Physics="Yes" mod="1" descr="">
  <Geometry>
    <Location URL="@/object/discored.w3d" ModelResource="discored"/>
    <Appearance URL=""/>
    <Position X="-239,191" Y="-377,68" Z="-1834.29"/>
    <Rotation X="90" Y="0" Z="155.89"/>
    <Scale X="1.5" Y="1.5" Z="1.5"/>
  </Geometry>
  <Behaviour>

```

```

    <OnProximity Distance="200" Persistence="0">
      <Action Type="ChangeColor" Property="#1C5981"/>
    </OnProximity >
  </Behaviour>
</Object>

```

Listing 12 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing an instance of ChangeColor action

The Property parameter is the hexadecimal value of the desired colour.

ChangeTexture

ChangeTexture allows to create a new texture e attach it to the desired objects; it is often used to reflect in the 3D world some response to server side events.

The events that can activate this action are : *Clicks OnMouseOver, OnProximity, OnSync*.

Its interaction control model is the following.

Figure 33 – ChangeTexture action

An example of use of this action in the XML configuration code:

```

<Object Name="Boardlab" Physics="Yes" mod="1" descr="">
  <Geometry>
    <Location URL="@/object/board1.w3d" ModelResource="board1"/>
    <Appearance URL=""/>
    <Position X="-239,191" Y="-377,68" Z="-1834.29"/>
    <Rotation X="90" Y="0" Z="155.89"/>
    <Scale X="1.5" Y="1.5" Z="1.5"/>
  </Geometry>
  <Behaviour>
    <OnSync NameSharedObj="textures" value="1">

```

```

    <Action Type="ChangeTexture" Property="@/contents/session2/img/frasi/fraseA.bmp"/>
  </OnSync>
</Behaviour>
</Object>

```

Listing 13 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing an instance of ChangeTexture action

The *Property* parameter contains the path of the bitmap image that will be loaded and shown as texture on the desired object.

Showtooltip

ShowToolTip shows an overlay message on the 3D windows when the pointer is over a specific object as defined in the XML configuration file, it is for example useful to know which are avatar names, as they are not shown in the rendered scene.

The event that can activate this action is *OnMouseOver*.

Its interaction control model is the following.

Figure 34 – ShowToolTip action

An example of use of this action in the XML configuration code:

```

<Object Name="discorosso" Physics="Yes" mod="1" descr="">
  <Geometry>
    <Location URL="@/object/discored.w3d" ModelResource="discored"/>
    <Appearance URL=""/>
    <Position X="-239,191" Y="-377,68" Z="-1834.29"/>
    <Rotation X="90" Y="0" Z="155.89"/>
    <Scale X="1.5" Y="1.5" Z="1.5"/>
  </Geometry>

```

```

<Behaviour>
  <OnMouseOver CursorType="256">
    <Action Type="ShowToolTip" Property="Disco Rosso"/>
  </ OnMouseOver >
</Behaviour>
</Object>

```

Listing 14 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing an instance of ShowToolTip action

StarTrek

StarTrek is used to move in position or environment different from the actual one.

Usually it is activated by the OnProximity event, and then form a direct user interaction, but it also can be activated by a server side event (*OnSync*).

The Property parameter is the *part* in which the user has to be teleported.

Its interaction control model is the following.

Figure 35 – StarTrek action

An example of use of this action in the XML configuration code:

```

<Behaviour>
  <OnProximity Distance="50" Persistence="1">
    <Action Type="StarTrek" Property="Part2"/>
  </OnProximity>
</Behaviour>

```

Listing 15 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing an instance of StarTrek action

SendSharedObj

This action allows to send to the server any message related to the status change of the remote Shared Objects in reaction to events such as mouse clicks, but also more in general as normal user interaction

Its interaction control model is the following.

Figure 36 – DragObject action

An example of use of this action in the XML configuration code:

```

<UserA1>
  <OnLeftClick>
    <Action Type="SendSharedObj" Property="clicks"/>
  </ OnLeftClick>
</UserA1>
  
```

Listing 16 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing an instance of DragObject action

The *Property* parameter represents the shared object name to be sent to the server whenever it changes its status (when user A1 mouse clicks on something).

goToUrl

This action is used to open the browser window selectively on some client or in general on all clients.

The web page shown in browser window is given by the value of the parameter *Property*

Its interaction control model is the following.

Figure 37 – DragObject action

An example of use of this action in the XML configuration code:

```

<Object Name="Boardses01" Physics="Yes" mod="1" descr="">
  <Geometry>
    <Location URL="@/object/board_S2_1.W3D" ModelResource="board_S2_1"/>
    <Appearance URL=""/>
    <Position X="969.2983" Y="-1408.298" Z="-5809.896"/>
    <Rotation X="90" Y="0" Z="34.7364"/>
    <Scale X="2" Y="2" Z="2"/>
  </Geometry>
  <Behaviour>
    <OnLeftClick>
      <Action Type="GoToUrl" Property="@/contents/ses3/world_html/board1.htm"/>
    </OnLeftClick>
    <OnMouseOver CursorType="280">
      </OnMouseOver>
  </Behaviour>
</Object>
  
```

Listing 17 - Fragment of the WT04 XML schema representing an instance of goToUrl action

4 Mobile WebTalk

In this chapter it's documented the last extension to the WT04 framework that allows it to interoperate with different mobile devices extending the concept of collaboration to the ubiquitous user.

4.1 Introduction

Collaborative Virtual Environments can be considered the result of the convergence of interests and research studies both in virtual reality field and in the computer supported collaborative workgroup one. CVEs are applications that (re)create a multi-user virtual world, as two or three-dimensional graphical environments inhabited by users (represented as digital actors called “avatar”) that share with other users time, space and actions, cooperating together for a common goal. CVEs represent the natural multi-user extension of the traditional single-user Virtual Environment technology typically used in leisure and entertainment fields. This extension allows better support for a wide range of applications: communication between instructors and trainees (simulation and training applications), sharing data (for visually supported discussions of scientists or decision-makers) (CSCW), support for innovative teaching/learning, support for collaborative e-learning (CSCL), are all examples of use for shared virtual environments.

Within the CSCW community CVEs represent a technology that may support some aspects of social interaction not readily accommodated by technologies such as audio and videoconferencing and shared desktop applications. Studies of cooperative work in real-world environments have highlighted the important role of physical space as resource of negotiating social interaction, promoting peripheral awareness and sharing artifacts. Many researchers have focused on the significance of cooperation among learners. Johnson and Johnson³⁹ stated that students and staff are profoundly influenced by working together to accomplish a job. Previous studies⁴⁰ have continuously demonstrated that students learn better in groups than either alone.

Nevertheless, traditional (standalone and web-based) collaborative learning systems do not fully engage the users (especially undergraduate students), since they can not discover activities of peers until they sit in front of the computer and connect to the Internet. That is, a student who issues a learning activity can not be certain whether his peers would be aware of the activity. Students can only

interact with and affect the workspace which is virtually connected on the Internet. This lack of awareness may lead to doubt and inefficient interaction among students. As the lack of complete engagement may prevent positive interdependence and promotive interaction, many web-based collaborative learning environments are unlikely to have the same quality of service as face-to-face learning environment.

The **unawareness** of collaborative activity can be eliminated by informing students of the context of collaborative activity in the Internet workspace, regardless of whether students are connected to the Internet. **Context information** is defined as any information for characterizing an entity that is considered relevant to the interaction between a user and an application. Many applications such as mobile context-aware tour guide⁴¹ has demonstrated the utility of **context-awareness**. Therefore, in a web-based collaborative learning activity, students should be given the contextual information to make them aware of learning activity on the Internet.

Mobile technologies offer now the new opportunity of the “anytime-anywhere” computing, allowing users to access information, collaborate with colleagues far from their desktop station. This emergence of mobile devices and new forms of connectivity allows to portray new forms of collaborations, not limited to the traditional stationary workstation but tailored upon the capabilities of these new devices of support ubiquitous cooperation.

Mobile devices have the potential to integrate with other learning activities and materials in the environment. Devices can connect abstract information with physical spatial information. This can enable activities to be situated in a relevant physical space, where the space that one is engaged in includes the device but is not limited to the screen.

While mobile devices are being designed and evaluated as personal and lifelong learning devices, we focus on mobile devices as collaborative tools. Education-based computer systems are traditionally designed as ‘single-user’ systems. Work has been carried out to extend the desktop for use by multiple users⁴² and analyses

have examined its influence on collaborative styles of behaviour. Use of mobile technologies are of growing interest for children's play and learning, however, there is still relatively little understanding of the ways in which mobile technologies might be designed to best support copresent collaboration.

Nonetheless, as Danesh et al⁴³ suggest, the mobility of these devices opens up the potential for children's group collaboration. Rather than being limited to working with an allocated partner at a desktop computer, children can move around, interacting with many other children and in differing environments. Inkpen et al⁴⁴ examined the importance of mobility using questionnaires to examine children's preferences for where they would like to be able to interact with computers, and found that the second most popular response was outside (with the first being in their bedroom).

In this chapter we present UbiCrossWords, a software prototype built to explore the opportunities to support learning through an orientation game in a mixed reality environment. This prototype is built upon a general underlying framework (Mobile WebTalk) able to support in a flexible way both stationary and mobile systems through a collaborative mixed environment allowing to represent and map information from one platform to a second one with different display and computing capabilities. We explore the use of heterogeneous collaboration (especially directed to educational purpose) through the design of a software architecture, running on mobile devices compatible with J2ME. Mobile WebTalk is able to configure, on every device, its own user view and environmental interactions on the basis of a XML based configuration description in order to represent workspace and interaction rules shared with the 3D stationary users.

4.2 Related work

Computer science, information systems, and educational research contribute to knowledge on mobile learning. Lepper and Malone⁴⁵ propose a relationship between learning and intrinsic motivation. Their research is based on an investigation of students playing videogames. Their result was to identify seven key factors for creating an intrinsically motivating instructional environment:

challenge, curiosity, control, fantasy, cooperation, competition, and recognition. Moreover, Lepper and Cordova⁴⁶ experimentally found that computer games raise the efficiency of learning if they increase the intrinsic motivation and link the goals ‘winning the game’ and ‘learning the material’. In these games, mathematical problem solving is embedded in an artificial game context. With the new mobile technology it is now possible to situate problems in their natural context without losing the motivational benefits of games. Prensky⁴⁷ try to understand the question “How do computer games engage players?” proposing six structural elements characterize games. There are:

1. *rules*, that organize the game,
2. *goals* and *objectives*, the players strive to achieve,
3. *outcome* and *feedback*, which measure the progress against the goals,
4. *conflict*, *competition*, *challenge*, and *opposition* leading to players’ excitement,
5. *interaction*, the social aspect in the game, and
6. the *representation or story* exaggerating interesting aspects of reality.

These elements need to be carefully designed and combined to create a fun and engaging game¹.

In a thorough literature review on game-based learning, Mitchell and Savill-Smith⁴⁸ show that these elements can be used to analyse games. For example, games for teaching basic skills, like reading and foreign languages, teaching society skills, and social learning such as encouraging successful dialogue. It should be possible to use these elements to carefully design and analyse mobile games, but so far this has not been done yet. There are already a few mobile systems that integrate playing and learning, such as the **Cooties Game** or **Geney**⁴⁹ or **Savannah**⁵⁰. They focus on role-play or simulation. Prototypes and commercial products of location-based games in a real life environment, like **CYSMN**⁵¹, **Pirates**⁵² or **Mogi**⁵³, show that people like to play with the new options, but these games focus purely on entertainment.

¹ We will use those factors to discuss design issues and the effects of the UbiCrossWords trying to emphasize collaboration activities between mobile and stationary users.

In our survey we found that the existing applications mostly fail to provide mobile users with access to the resources and tools that can be relevant for an ongoing collaboration. In particular, mobile applications fail to provide users with an adequate collaboration context, i.e. a shared workspace, suitable for ubiquitous learning activities.

In fact, almost all of them were applications, rather than flexible frameworks: they required extensive reprogramming for being used in different situations and for different purposes, being also inherently oriented towards code construction in a *code-centered* fashion.

We wanted, instead, to create a general “format” that could be used over and over, designing our application in a declarative way using simple authoring tools, thus using a declarative approach since the environment can be automatically generated from this declarative descriptions.

We believe that if properly designed, shared workspace applications can be as useful in supporting mobile users as they are for non-mobile ones. Furthermore we think that a heterogeneous workspace, made up of mobile and stationary users, could be much more effective than a traditional one. This is because the “anytime anywhere” access to group information for the mobile users allows to develop shared workspace with support for contextualized communication (real world information) towards either the same mobile users and the non-mobile ones that can experience multi sensorial, on field information that they could never get thought their traditional virtual environment. On the other hand, stationary users, having more powerful devices than the mobile ones, can more easily access complex information, allocating vastly different cognitive resources to a display (i.e. the computer monitor) than a person in the field who needs to pay attention to the external environment, e.g. traffic.

Then our main targets were:

- Extend and partially re-design the **WT04 framework** to become a *flexible multidevice collaborative framework*, that will be called **Mobile**

WebTalk, able to integrate different devices making multiple heterogeneous users to collaborate together.

- Define a mobile learning experience (**UbiCrossWords**) in order to test the above framework
- Implement UbiCrossWords as instance of the Mobile WebTalk framework.

4.3 Key Factors

In most CVEs, main and the only shared workspace is the 3D virtual world, a sort of stage through which users navigate and perform interactions. The key component of this kind of shared experience is dominated by the paradigm **WYSIWIS** (What You See Is What I See) (Figure 38), that is a form of synchronization support to the real time sharing and manipulation of the information. WYSIWIS technique allows users to be represented in the same virtual environment, having in this way an homogeneous view of the surrounding 3D world, even if from different point of view; furthermore they can point and discuss about an object on the screen being sure it can also be viewed by their collaborators. The use and spread of such technique in previous traditional groupware systems was a difficult but not impossible task as they could rely on common technical platform.

On the other hand, technological developments in mobile, embedded and pervasive devices provide designers with an opportunity to better support existing forms of collaborative work, by providing the user with additional computing capabilities, yet delivering this through a ubiquitous channel. Whereas a standard PC would physically limit the task to a fixed physical location, mobile technologies allow users to move around whilst simultaneously accessing information from the digital and the real world. Mobile devices have the potential to integrate with other learning activities and materials in the environment. Devices can connect abstract information with physical spatial information.

This can enable activities to be situated in a relevant physical space, where the space that one is engaged in includes the device but is not limited to the screen.

Moving from the traditional desktop computer to mobile, palm sized computers present new opportunities also for learning. Mobile devices have the potential to augment physical activity spaces and enable frequent, integral computer use rather than the occasional and supplementary use of desktop computers. This shift may be particular appropriate in cases where the learning process began an interactive and collaborative experience. However, collaboration and education will only occur if the technology is designed to fit within the context of use which is intended. Although the WYSIWIS idealization recognizes that efficient reference to common objects depends on a common view of the work at hand, strict WYSIWIS was found to be too limiting and relaxed versions were proposed to accommodate personalized screen layouts⁵⁴.

In fact, all the above factors result in the mobile user and the stationary user using different applications and working with semantically equivalent but different information on platforms and in environments that are also very different.

Our main key point is that heterogeneous collaboration should follow a **WYSINWIS** (What You See Is NOT What I See) approach where every user's action is interactively and continuously reflected in other users' workspaces, but with a varying degree of accuracy or realism or through a qualitatively different visualization. We advocate the semantically difference between "work space" , the virtual or real environment were users meets each other and interact directly, and the "collaboration space" which is the environment within users different for technology (mobile and stationary), role (teachers, students, committees, etc.) or specific target interact indirectly but being aware of each other presence and aims.

In this work we address the challenges related to the developing mobile collaboration environments, with particular focus on shared workspaces. As requirements for such application can deeply vary depending on the specific collaborative settings, the support must therefore be conceived not in form of single application but rather in form of an environment assuring the required flexibility and above all an high degree of mutual awareness between heterogeneous users.

4.4 WYSIWIS and WYSINWIS

“Awareness” plays an important role in CSCW systems. According to Greenberg, Gutwin and Cockburn⁵⁵ there are four different kinds of “awareness” in CSCW traditional systems:

- *Workspace awareness* is about who is present in the workspace, where they are, and what they are doing;
- *Informal awareness* means that the general sense of who is around and what they are depending on;
- *Social awareness* is the information that a person maintains about others in a social or conversational context;
- *Group-structured awareness* involves knowledge about such things as people’s roles and responsibilities, their positions on an issue, their status, and group process.

Main aspect in a collaborative work is the *workspace awareness*, that is the instantaneous perception to interact within a shared workspace with one or more users. The basic meaning of awareness in traditional collaborative systems is to know who the collaborators are, what they are doing, what they have done and what they want to do. In other words, in WYSIWIS CVE systems, awareness is achieved sharing the same conception of space (the shared stage where users move) and the same notion of time, that is the instantaneous events propagations within the virtual world (avatars’ movements, environment reactions to each action performed etc.).

WYSIWIS (Figure 38) is the aim of most synchronous CSCW systems. Synchronous systems do not only want to support the same views to the shared documents, as shown in Figure 38, but also the shared views of each collaborator, because in a face-to-face environment, all the collaborators share the views to the environment.

WYSIWIS approach, intrinsically emphasizing that collaboration requires the commonalities among the collaborators, doesn’t suite well to all situations characterized by considerable technological differences, and above all if the collaboration has to be achieved when users use different communication and

work device (i. e desktop computer vs mobile devices) and different space-temporal notions (real world for mobile users vs virtual world for stationary users).

Figure 38 - WYSIWIS: the same views to the same shared objects

Personalized groupware should offer a system that conforms to the individual need of participants and of groups. Chang, K.H. H. et⁵⁶ al mentioned a WYSINWIS style in their collaborative writing tool for user's own viewing spaces. We suggest the terminology WYSINWIS to emphasize the differences among peoples' requirement to different inputs and outputs (Figure 39).

Figure 39 – WYSINWIS: different views to the same shared objects

We think that an effective collaboration can be achieved even if between heterogeneous (technologically different) sub-environment, if users can share similar notions of space and time:

- *time*: some of the events raised in one of the sub-environments can be propagated in all other sub-environments, thus giving the sense of time synchronicity between them;
- *space*: the sense of mutual position given in a generic 3D CVE by the avatar's virtual world coordinates can be associated and translated in the real world position for mobile users.

In other worlds mobile users while moving, could be provided with a geo-position tracker (i.e. a simple GPS receiver) which gathers data about their geo-referred position; this information is then forwarded to the central communication system which takes care of the maintenance and the consistency of the shared state. In this way also the 3D sub-environment could be aware of the *presence* of mobile users, for example having a 2D map of their position added to the CVE. On the other hand, mobile users can be kept informed of 3D CVE virtual users in a huge number of ways, mainly depending on the device capabilities and the degree of connectivity and bandwidth available (flat or dial up, broadband UMTS or simply GPRS)

4.5 mobile learning scenario

This chapter introduces the UbiCrossWords through a usage scenario. The usage scenario is needed to understand the effects, and the system architecture is needed as a basis for the discussion of design issues.

UbiCrossWords is used to support undergraduate students, aged between 14 and 19 years old, in on field learning activities linked to cultural heritage.

Players equipped with handheld interfaces move through the city. Sensors capture information about the players' current context, which the game uses to deliver an experience that changes according to their locations, actions, and, potentially, feelings. This information are transmitted (through a Wi-Fi or gprs network) to other players, on the streets (mobile users) or connected online from their desktop workstations (stationary users). The net result is an cultural game that interleaves a player's everyday experience of the city with the extraordinary experience of a game.

Users are divided into two teams, each one composed of both mobile and stationary users.

The general aim is to complete the crossword puzzle before the opposite team. To gain a definition each team has to find hidden objects in a treasure hunt fashion: objects are both physical and virtual but all regarding a specific topic given to the competing teams.

The whole experience is structured as a cooperative and competitive game. Each group has to complete their task list (on the basis of the given topic) but, in the same time, has to avoid concurrent players that try to block and catch them in some way. Cooperation rules force group members to meet members from other groups as well as teachers and to exchange information with them – again they are supported with location-based information on their displays. The given tasks provide them with basic information on the cultural heritage and the history of the city of Lecce. There are the following types of tasks for mobile users:

- *Significant place tasks*: The students have to find important or typical places such as the oldest baroque Church , the place where ancient Romans fought . At each location, they have to perform a task (answer a multiple choice question, take a picture of something, etc.). The specific tasks may be context-dependent (they depend not only on the location, but also on the time of the day or they build on the activity of some previous group). The task execution is supported by the handheld device (e.g. serving as a front-end to the information system or providing them with needed information).
- *Significant people tasks*: The students have to find important or typical people of the city and have to interview them on their activities.
- *Significant event tasks*: The significant events can be scheduled or come as surprise.

Each task requires the group to answer one or more simple questions displayed on the handheld device. For example, one task might be to find the Cathedral main altar. There they get the question ‘What are the sentence on the top of the altar’. They won’t get the next task until the correct answer is given. In addition to

the game, the students can annotate real objects with virtual ‘post-it’s’. Other groups can read these short messages and answer with their own post-it’s.

There are the following types of tasks for stationary online users:

- *Physical skill tasks*: are tasks related to the ability of fine move and control the avatar, to fly , to jump, etc. Examples are the Treasure Hunt a cultural game in witch users are asked to find some hidden objects, according to the topic give by the super user. They has to be quick to find objects, and every time an object is discovered, they have answer a question to gain the definition for the puzzle. Another example is the flying platform game where avatars have to jump from a platform to another without falling to catch first the flag.
- *Cultural skill tasks*: are tasks related to the knowledge of the game topic, most used tool is chat to collaborate with other team mate and choose the right answer to every given question.

4.5.1 The online players’ experience

There are two kind of stationary players: 3D players represented by an avatar in the virtual world and chat players, without any embodiment able, only to interact with other users by chat.

3D players can move through a 3D model of the city center (now in supported only the city of Lecce) with a fixed maximum speed, access a city map view, see other players’ and mobile users’ positions, and exchange text messages with them. Online players start at the UbiCrossWords Web page, where they can explore background information about the game, including instructions on how to play. They enter their username and then join the online experience environment being dropped into a highly abstract 3D model of the hosting city. The model shows the streets’ layout and outline models of key buildings but doesn’t feature textures or details of dynamic objects such as cars or, of course, most of the population. Online players see themselves represented as running avatars, similar to the other players. Online players use the arrow keys to run around this model. They cannot enter solid buildings, move out of the game zone, or cross several fences. When

the game starts, a task list is given to each stationary player, referring to significant places, people and events. They are hints to find places where are hidden the “virtual objects”, every time the find an object they are asked to answer a question (in text format) to gain a new definition for the UbiCrossWords puzzle and the opportunity to fill its schema. On the other hand online stationary players must avoid the mobile players. If a mobile user gets close to an online player, the player is blocked for a while. Scoring is based on the number of correct definition found by each team.

Online players finally can view and enter text messages. Figure 40 shows an example online player’s interface, with the player’s avatar in the foreground and a runner close by in the background. Figure 1b shows the interface in map mode.

Figure 40 - Online player 3D interface

Chat players’ aim is to help the theirs own teams mate, to complete the crossword schema by answering at the definitions.

At the beginning of the game, the chat users are asked to answer to some question related to the crossword topic to get definitions. So they have to chat by each other, and to try to give the right answer to collect the crossword definitions. During the second phase, users are asked to fill the crossword schema answering to the definition collected during the first game phase.

Figure 41 - Chat players' interface

4.5.2 The mobile players' experience

The mobile players' move through the streets of the city centre and can see online players' and other mobile players' positions on a handheld map and see the players' text messages. The game delivers the mobile' interface on an Qtek 9100 handheld computer from a central server to maintain the shared state over an 802.11b wireless local area network or GPRS connection. A GPS receiver plugged into the PDA's serial port registers a runner's position, which is sent back to the server over the wireless network. Given the PDA's small screen size, mobile users are forced to view the environment in map mode being able to zoom between a global view and a close-up local view centred on their current position. They carried digital cameras (integrated in the PDAs) so that they could photograph the physical location where they performed dome activity. Also for mobile users there's a task list, they are asked to find physical places on the basis of the some hints. When approaching to this place (i.e. POI – Point of Interest) the GPS antenna receive actual coordinates, sends it to the server and, if the position is correct gives the opportunity to gain a new definition for the UbiCrossWords puzzle helping their team to win the match completing the game.

Figure 42 - The mobile players interface: on the left the map with the chat and the user picture, on the right the shared crosswords interface

4.6 The Framework: Mobile WebTalk

Mobile WebTalk is the fifth release of a framework being developed and updated from 1998, that allows to design, configure and generate flexible 3D Collaborative Mixed Virtual Environment in which users can meet, interact and learn in a collaborative fashion.

Main key point of this architecture are:

- to provide a flexible and highly decoupled development environment to allow different developer teams to design and deploy specific mixed (desktop 3D, mobile 2D) collaborative environments dealing with only the specific task (3D design, contents assembling, story board design, software develop) they are expert in, without regarding any other task.
- to allow to easily define and set up collaborative learning sessions' prototype, meant as set of linked shared environments that work as a mere place where the action takes place sharing the same kind of virtual experience (be it educational, entertaining, informative..), main collaboration features and the same environmental containers, from which derive different, context specific instances of virtual world, well suited for different users and situations;

- to convey these environments a high sense of virtual presence, leaving the full graphic driven paradigm WYSIWIS to switch towards a new one that takes the overall application design into account and to provide a set of interaction features to drive the collaboration among users in the specific way the designer was intended to do;
- design a central collaboration engine, able to integrate technologically different devices with heterogeneous capabilities and to maintain coherent the shared state, in order to allow multiple users to interact and collaborate each one using his own device peculiarities.

4.6.1 System Architecture

Mobile Webtalk is a web-based system in which the handheld computers (Qtek 9100) carried by the students and the desktop computers act as mobile clients to a central communication server.

The mobile clients have integrated 802.11g wireless networking capabilities, a full colour screen, a sound system, 512Mb of file storage containing all the contents used in the experience and an attached GPS unit (chip SiRF Star IIe/LP, 12 sat channels).

These capabilities allow the mobile clients to:

- determine their locations in the outdoor game area;
- accept inputs from the users in the form of button events (i.e. to answer a question);
- transmit location information and user interface events to the remote communication server over the wireless network;
- accept responses from the communication server that requires individual clients to display a picture or a message, play a sound file on the client's screen.

Stationary desktop clients allows students to see and control their avatars in the 3D environment as well as to see mobile users represented as running avatars.

Stationary desktop clients are able to:

- represent every mobile user as avatar with the position sent by the communication server;
- accept inputs from the users in the form of mouse events and keyboard keypress (i.e. to open a question board, to move the avatar);
- accept responses from the communication server that requires individual clients to display a picture or a message, play a sound file on the client's screen.

The communication server uses the information received from the mobile clients to determine what happens in the mixed environment and thus what the students experience. For example, the server interprets incoming location information from the clients with respect to maps that relate the virtual environment to the physical game space.

As a result, the server may instruct a client to render a sound, image or scent that represents something that a student would encounter at that location in the virtual environment, such as a question board or another avatar.

4.6.2 Technical Architecture

Mobile Webtalk (Figure 43) is made of three different subsystems:

Figure 43- Mobile WebTalk architecture

- *Desktop Client side*

The “world engine” is the client-side of the application. Through a number of modules, it manages the connection with the server and controls the rendering on the client machine. The “interaction engine”, in particular, controls the collaboration features, while “world builder” renders in real time the scene, according with the shared state of all the objects and avatars.

- *Communication Server Side*

- Contents Repositories: they store all the geometries and the textures, created at design time.
- XML files repository: it stores all the different configuration (XML) files representing the starting setup of every collaborative session, as well as the rules according to the action can evolve.
- Communication Server: it keeps the actual shared state, keeping track, for example, of positions, rotations, and “state” in general all the avatars and objects. Any change of the shared state is detected and send to all the clients, raising an “onSync” signal.
- *Mobile WT Server:*
 - accepts and keeps connection requests by mobile users
 - forwards events and actions towards other mobile or stationary users.

- *SMS Gateway:* handles the SMS queue to and from every mobile user

- *Mobile Client side*

Clients side application are written in Java using J2ME platform (MIDP 2.0 profile). This choice ensures all the functionalities needed, without regarding of the particular device where the application will be execute because of the cross platform feature granted by Java. Each client is then composed by 5 main components:

- *Mobile World Parser:* loads the XML declarative description of the mobile session and configures, at run time, the application to listen certain events (proximity, time, onSync, etc.) and to perform certain actions.

- *GPS Handler*: connects and parses data from GPS external aerial which is responsible of receiving the geostationary satellites' actual position, and finally sends data to Collaboration Engine
- *Collaboration Engine*: it's the core of the mobile application, receives inputs form *Mobile World Parser* and *GPS Handler* in form of events which it has to react to and action to be performed for each event;
- *Connection Adapter*: manages connections towards central *Mobile WT Server*

Canvas Handler: manages the drawing and the scrolling of the 2D map on the device's display, also provides the representation of the POIs (Points Of Interest) onto the map, on the basis of the configuration data of the *Mobile Session XML file*

4.7 Flexibility Issues

Mobile WebTalk architecture is natively based on a declarative description, using the XML standard as a configuration language, giving in this way the possibility of “describing” static features (e.g. representing position, color, dimension etc. of the objects at start-up) and a dynamic features (e.g. defining if objects can be moved, clicked etc.), instead of “hard coding” them, that was essential to gain configurability and flexibility.

4.7.1 Collaborative Metaphors

While designing the Mobile WebTalk framework for the support of heterogeneous users we wanted to keep a high degree of configurability in order to accomplish the highly flexible manner in which collaboration among real people happens. In fact different groups require different functionality based on their domain of collaboration, their culture of collaboration, the group processes they use, etc. It is therefore highly desirable that a groupware platform can be tailored to the specific groups using it. Flexibility in *Mobile WebTalk* is achieved through a tailorable collaboration model based on *collaborative metaphors* concept which is at the basis of the Mobile WebTalk framework.

Collaborative Metaphors are set of rules to support interaction and collaboration between users who want to explore complex content and information together. The rules determines how the “collaborative community” can be created and managed, how every member of the community can operate on his/her own or can cooperate with other members. Different types of situation, tasks and users roles determine different behaviors and therefore need different metaphors.

Mobile WebTalk architecture offers a huge support to collaborative metaphors. We can set up in the XML world configuration file a set of specific behaviors that can be applied to a specific metaphor. So we can select what behavior is applied to a specific shared object in a particular moment. When the specific collaborative metaphor is activated, the corresponding set of interaction rules take effect, and every object uses the right behavior to interact with the “shared world”. Thanks to the Collaborative Metaphor paradigm, we are able to manage complex

interactions between entities in a virtual shared environment, specifying the current set of collaboration's rules governing every aspect of the virtual world. Obviously, defining a huge number of metaphors and melting them together, we can govern the collaborative environment recreating the exact collaborative situation we wanted. We wanted to inherit the same flexibility also in configuration of the mobile sub-environment, then we devised an extended collaboration model (see chapter **WebTalk Collaboration Model**) made of entities, actions and events that could have sense in real world usage as their corresponding had in the CVE one.

4.7.2 Declarative Environment Description

The entire flexibility of this system is demanded to the XML session formal description which can represent every single interaction capability of the system both the local one, between user and its mobile device, and the remote one between mobile and stationary users. Once the heterogeneous collaborative session has started each mobile and desktop client connects to the central server which maintains a copy of the XML configuration file representing, in a declarative form of scene graph, the structure of either the desktop session or the mobile one.

Each mobile client loads a copy of the XML configuration file, an example is shown below:

```
<?xml version="1.0"?>
<World>
  <Configuration>
    <FCServer Uri="/WebTalk3_3/session2.xml" ip="193.204.yyy.xxx"/>
    <JavaServerPort value="4444"/>
  </Configuration>
  <Part num="1" url="" descr="Firs Part of the environment">
    <Object Name="SCroce_church" Lat="403328" Long="181157" Active="1">
      <OnProximity Far="5">
        <Action Type="AskQuestion" Text="In which year S. Croce church was built?"
A="1492" B="1500" C="1592" D="1620" E="1700" F="1750" Answer="3"/>
      </OnProximity>
    </Object>
  </Part>
</World>
```

```
</Object>
</Part>
</World>
```

Listing 18 - Sample of the XML configuration file of Mobile WebTalk

The XML configuration file is basically made of two different parts:

- the *configuration* element: containing configuration parameter as the IP address of the central server, the port number and so on
- the *part* element: describes the different section in which the environment is divided

Every part is “populated” by interactive elements, in other world entities provided with a *behaviour*.

For mobile users, interactive elements are above all POIs, geo-referred points characterized by a fixed latitude and longitude. While walking the GPS receiver sends position data to the application; once the user approaches a POI (which position is defined in one of *Object* elements) the engine reacts to the event *OnProximity* performing a reaction specified in the element *Action*.

Most important action types are:

- *AskQuestion*: shows a text question on the mobile device display;
- *SendRemoteObject*: sends a text message or a picture taken with the device embedded camera, to one or more remote user (both mobile and stationary);
- *goToUrl*: opens a new browser window on a specific page;
- *ChangeColor* or *ChangePicture*: changes the color or the picture of the specified shared object;
- *Vibrate*: enable device vibration;
- *PlaySound*: play an audio file;

supported events are:

- *OnProximity*: raised when the mobile user approaches a POI;

- *OnClick*: raised when a mobile user selects an interactive object on the device screen;
- *OnSync*: raised when an external interactive object, such as 3D objects in the virtual environment, changes some of its properties, this may occur for example when a 3D user clicks on an object: the reaction could be not only an action performed inside the 3D world (i.e. the object changes its colour) but it can affect also the mobile users' environment and vice versa.

OnSync events is the main “bridge” between mobile and desktop environments, in the sense that it allows the events to propagate between heterogeneous environments; this collaboration model separating events and actions on different environments, leaves the freedom to define how each client application (mobile or stationary) could interpret it, performing similar or completely different reactions. For example, a user in the 3D virtual world, that clicks on an interactive object such as a board, could raise in its own environment the opening of a web page containing a multimedia question and in the mobile one could result in showing a simple text question. On the other hand the result could be very different as well: the mobile is given the target to find some place (for example the S. Croce Church), its mobile device application detects when he, while moving, approaches the interested POI and notifies it on the 2D map on the display, at the same time propagates event towards 3D users that suddenly see appearing a 3D object in form of church in front of them.

In this case the same activity of discovering a place results in different visualization and interaction rules according to the previously mentioned paradigm: WYSINWIS

4.8 Framework Testing Scenario

The Mobile Webtalk framework as described above was evaluated in a user test at the University of Lecce (Italy) in April 2006, rooms used for the indoor test were covered by a good wireless LAN signal. At the moment of this test stationary and mobile subsystems weren't fully integrated so some of the features (like catching) were not evaluated.

4.8.1 Participants

A total of 36 students volunteered to participate to three different test session. They were divided in 2 different teams composed by 6 student (2 in the desktop 3d environment, 2 playing as chat users, 2 with the mobile device). They were aged between 19 and 24 years old. There were all experienced computer users. Game topic was university life.

4.8.2 The game

The game consisted in compiling a collaborative crossword puzzle finding the definitions in different ways (as explained in chapter 5:

- the users with the 3D desktop, to gain their definitions, participated to a treasure hunt to find the hidden objects in the virtual environment representing some of the rooms of the Innovation Engineering Dept.;
- chat users were asked to answer a set of questions related to the universities courses (such as computer science questions)
- mobile users (each user has a mobile device connected through the wireless connection to the shared environment) were asked to perform a list of task, each one consisting of a location they had to find and a location related question.

All the users involved in the game could communicate with others using the chat. The game lasted approximately 60min. In this time, the students had the opportunity to answer the questions and to chat with other with the students of their team. At the end of each game, each player was given a questionnaire.

The questionnaire contained 15 questions that can be clustered into 3 sections: the first section asked the students how satisfied they were with their introduction to the game; the second section collected data on the motivational aspects of the game; the third section focused on the usability of individual functions.

All the game phases were governed by expert super users (guides) that took care to keep alive interest, action and provide some help to participants.

4.8.3 Discussion framework

As said previously, UbiCrossWords can be described in terms of Prensky's six structural elements. The scenario describes the global *rules*. Each player has the *goal* to solve the tasks (actions, questions, etc.) and ultimately learn. The real time collaborative framework gives direct *feedback* on the current status in the game and on the *outcome* achieved so far. *Conflicts and competition* are realised through the opportunity to gain points (by solving tasks or catching others) against the opponent team. By playing in groups there is *interaction* in the game. This effect is additionally supported by the chat function. The *representation* is realized through implementation of the WYSINWIS paradigm: the orientation is achieved for 3D online users through the 3D virtual model in which they play; for mobile users on the digital map; there's no orientation issues for mere chat users. These structural elements characterised our game and should engage the player.

4.8.4 Results

We asked the participants whether it was fun to play the game. Most of students (10 of the 12) indicated that they liked it and would play it again any time. Two participants liked it, but thought playing it once was enough. Nobody chose the option 'It was a waste of time'. Enthusiastic comments in the open questions supports these findings. So the game is entertaining and students like to play it. Then the students were asked to vote for the three most significant game key issue from a technical point of view. They can select up to 3 answer. The table below shows the results.

<i>Most important positive aspects (maximum three choices)</i>	
The position tracking on a map is a significant value added during the game.	12
This game is more interesting than a static game.	8
The opportunity to independently explore the collaborative world is a value added	6
The user interface was friendly and helped to play	3

Table 2 - Most important positive aspects of the experience

<i>Most important negative aspects (maximum three choices)</i>	
The difficult typing of text on a mobile device has effectively hindered me to send chat messages	2
the mobile screen could not be read in some conditions	2
I had great difficulties to keep an overview over different visualizations	1

Table 3 - Most important negative aspects of the experience

4.9 Lesson Learned and Conclusions

The developing and the indoor test performed on UbiCrossWords over the Mobile WebTalk framework provided a deeper insight into some of the issues related to mobile learning. The questionnaires report the participants enjoyed the experience and most would have liked to play it again. We addressed this finding to their exciting mixed reality experience. Mixed reality means that the participants activities are partially represented in physical space and partially in digital space and both spaces stand in correlation to one another as exemplified by the orientation with a map and by the shared crossword game (Figure 44).

Figure 44 - UbiCrossWords mixed environment

The UbiCrossWords allowed the participants to collectively immerse in such a mixed reality. However we found that the value added of the use of mobile devices is at the top only when tasks given to players are location relevant. A great care has to be taken to the task design taking into account: the effect of the limited accuracy of the position detection, also amplified by information delay over the Wi-Fi LAN. Moreover also the design of the task interaction itself is difficult: allowing for open questions can make the game much richer and more challenging. However, the users have to write down the answer with the pen and a small virtual keyboard on the PDA, which is difficult to use. Multiple choice questions restrict the game design and are said to be didactically poor, but users can answer with a simple click.

On the other hand stationary users can benefit of the on field activity performed by mobile users giving them a deeper sense of immersion in the mixed environment that finally reflects in a higher learning degree.

From a more technical point of view, while developing the UbiCrossWords game, as instance of the Mobile WebTalk framework, we experienced a high level of flexibility in the configuration and fine set up of the mixed environment,

respect to the old version of WebTalk. Through our approach, based on Collaborative Metaphors, we was able to simplify and formalize the interaction rules between users in different context of use (with different roles, device capabilities, etc.)

Moreover this approach allow to easily generate multiple streams of similar applications simply editing and modifying the XML configuration file, thus dramatically reducing the timing for customizing a collaborative learning session.

Next step will be evolve the platform to support extended interaction modalities, fully realizing the scenario of ubiquitous collaboration. This will be done mainly widening the number of supported basic *Actions* and *Events* inside the environment, which, arranged together, can represent more complex interaction situations and behaviors.

PART 3

5 Conclusions and Future Work

This chapter we will present the final conclusion about the work done and about how each objective has been reached as well as it will draw the lines of the next research works on this field

The study and the development of a multi channel collaborative system, that provides adaptive mechanism of visualization either on two or on three dimension, is a complex problem that needs the research of solutions about important technical and conceptual problems.

Several different software systems, both commercial as Active Worlds⁶ and Blaxxun⁵⁷ and research prototypes as Dive⁵, SPLINE⁷ and MASSIVE-3⁹, support today *Collaborative Virtual Environments*, but, even if they propose interesting ideas about the topological architecture of the system, by suggesting, for example, peer to peer system and, more recently, also solution based on distributed network as Globus, or by reaching a very high level of graphical realism, they still have several weak points:

- They often **require proprietary software** working as “standalone player” on each client , while we wanted to avoid the use of special plug-ins (since our primary target were public schools, where it is often difficult to install unusual SW).
- Most of the solutions were **applications**, rather than **flexible frameworks**: they required extensive reprogramming for being used in different situations and for different purposes, and often specific contents.
- Most environments emphasized **“quality” of graphics** (often intended as a kind of photo-realism), and **“real-world behavior”** (i.e. systematic replica of physics laws), rather than on collaborative features and/or engaging features, as we intended to have.
- The **authoring tools** they provide are often limited to each particular web-3D format. So most of 3D scenes generated are mostly monolithic and restricted with regard to both content and programming code reuse. Furthermore poor or no support was give to the **collaborative behavior design** and the **interaction control** as mean to stimulate certain kind of cooperation among users.

5.1 Innovative aspects in Webtalk

We believe that the WebTalk technology is innovative respect to all the other existing architectures, previously already examined by us, above all for its high applicative capabilities. Main features to be mentioned are:

- The most innovative element consists in a formal and configurable approach to the *collaborative metaphors*. In other words, WebTalk locate some basic elements for the cooperation and allow the designer to compose them, to create cooperation modalities that can be useful or significant in the specific applicative context that is being studied.
- Another great innovation is to bring the idea of total contents reuse and dynamically generation of the 3D navigational environment, providing a well defined semantic to describe the modalities in which the elements have to be composed, but also foreseeing the possibility to create new ones. It is then possible to collect contents only once, and then to present them in the 3D world in different forms, simply by re-describing the presentation rules or, in a following phase, using an automatic tool to build the virtual worlds.

In order to overcome the limitation mentioned above, we designed by scratch a new framework called WebTalk04 that:

- Worked as Macromedia/Adobe Shockwave and Flash plugin then could rely on the best and the more widespread player on the market, and, above all, was designed as **web application**, without any need of proprietary standalone software pre-installed.
- Was modeled on the concept of **Scene Graph** (see chapter 3.5.1 *Virtual world representation*) and **Behaviour** (see chapter 3.5.5 *Access control and behaviors*), defining a vocabulary of elements and a syntax to compose them to represent, in a declarative XML form (see chapter 3.4 *XML-based implementation*), either the static properties of the environment (geometries populating the world, starting positions, etc) or the dynamic ones, those one regulating the interactions within the virtual world. In this way, the notion of platform and of application are well separated, and the designer can deploy different applications by using the same parts, objects and templates. More over, it suffices to add objects, in any geometry format, to the database, and add to the XML description to

have the system generate the new application, without any code hacking and extensive reprogramming.

- Was based on the *Collaboration Control Model* (see chapter 3.5.5 *Access control and behaviors*) giving the possibility to a designer to compose a custom collaborative metaphor (see chapter 3.5.6 *Collaborative metaphors*). The system has a number of built-in cooperation patterns, which can be activated and deactivated to form a set. This set can be attached, via the user management module to each user, creating cooperation metaphors, rules with which the users interact within the world.

5.2 Results of Webtalk04

WebTalk04 had an extensive testing of the field, being deployed, in 5 months (year 2005), for two applications, Learning@Europe (involving 48 schools in 6 different countries and more than 900 students) and Stori@Lombardia (involving 36 schools in Northern Italy and more than 700 students). The two applications had different settings (world and objects) and similar (not equal) activities. Overall we had to implement and run 84 collaborative sessions (48 and 36, respectively), with 12 students and 2 staff members acting as users for each session.

WebTalk04 has proven to be a reliable environment, capable of handling difficult connecting situation (our main troubles, instead, stemmed by the fact that many times, despite our instructions, schools did not have the proper versions of plug-ins installed).

On the configuration side, the new features introduced by WT04 (the XML configuration facility and its authoring tools) have dramatically reduced the timing for “customizing a session”. The table below shows the estimated improvement, with respect to reprogram the sessions, by using an XML file, and by using the authoring tool. Also the reader should consider two additional factors: reprogramming requires to have at hand a specifically skilled person and also it requires additional testing (with all the corresponding risks).

SESSION TYPE	REPROGRAMMING (ESTIMATE)	MANUAL CONFIGURATION (TIME SPENT)	ASSISTED CONFIGURATION (TIME SPENT)
session1 L@E	2 hours	25 minutes	15 minutes
session2 L@E	3 hours	40 minutes	25 minutes
session3 L@E	2 hours	20 minutes	15 minutes
session4 L@E	2 hours	20 minutes	10 minutes

Table 4 - Average bandwidth usage measurements

5.3 Results of Mobile Webtalk

Mobile WebTalk has been the natural extension of this successful framework towards the multi device and multi channel field, opening the collaboration to virtually any mobile programmable device. It has been designed to maximize the experience done with WebTalk, transferring and evolving the concepts of *scene graph*, *behaviour*, and *collaborative metaphor*. In particular, it has been necessary to move from the traditional concept of *workspace awareness*, based on the paradigm **WYSIWIS** (What You See Is What I See) to a new one: **WYSINWIS** (What You See Is NOT What I See) (see chapter 4.4 *WYSIWIS and WYSINWIS*), to take into account the different capabilities of mobile handled device, respect to the stationary ones, such as lower computing power, smaller display and limited stand by time, but also their great power of pervasivity proper of the “*anywhere and anytime computing*” they are expression of.

We argued that *effective collaboration* can be achieved even if between heterogeneous (technologically different) sub-environment, if users can share similar notions of space and time:

- *time*: some of the events raised in one of the sub-environments can be propagated in all other sub-environments, thus giving the sense of time synchronicity between them;
- *space*: the sense of mutual position given in a generic 3D CVE by the avatar’s virtual world coordinates can be associated and translated in the real world position for mobile users.

Therefore we conceptually mapped the 3D environments users coordinates with the real world geo-referred coordinates. In this way also the 3D sub-environment could be aware of the *presence* of mobile users, for example having a 2D map of their position added to the CVE. On the other hand, mobile users can be kept informed of 3D CVE virtual users in a huge number of ways, mainly depending on the device capabilities and the degree of connectivity and bandwidth available (flat or dial up, broadband UMTS or simply GPRS)

Upon the Mobile WebTalk framework we implemented an application, **UbiCrossWorlds** (see chapter 4.8 *Framework Testing Scenario*) to perform a laboratory β -test of the new environment, this experimental phase involved 36 students (experience computer users).

From a first analysis of the test report, the positive result was reflected in the reliability of the whole technical environment as well as from the users reaction and impressions (see chapter 4.8.4 *Results*).

5.4 Next steps

Beside customization, work continues on two directions:

- Development of caching features, in order to pre-load geometries and multimedia content on the client machines, therefore reducing the initial troubles of each session (when large amount of data must be sent to each client).
- Development of a way to “gracefully degrade” performances if connection is very low (and European schools may have terrible connections). An example could be forbidding flying and other advanced features (only to the clients with poor connections), while retaining basic movements of avatars and chats, which are the essential features to take part in a collaborative session.
- Evolution of tools to generate the XML formal description of the virtual environment towards a toolkit able to manage all the different authoring phase of the whole lifecycle of a WebTalk application.
- Definition of a modeling language (maybe UML like or compliant) to represent a collaborative environment, able to abstract meaningful

elements and relations from all the technicalities proper of the current environmental formal description coded in XML .

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank Prof. Paolo Paolini and Prof. Luca Mainetti for their strength and continuous support; I would also like to thank all the members of WebTalk development team, especially my friends Eng. Ugo Barchetti and Eng. Stefano Santo Sabato.

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Bibliography

- ¹ F.FIT and O.S. GmbH. BSCW (Basic Support for Cooperative Work), 2005. <<http://bscw.fit.fraunhofer.de/>>.
- ² Groove Networks. <<http://www.groove.net/home/index.cfm>>.
- ³ C. Blanchard et al., “A Reality Built for Two: A Virtual Reality Tool,” ACM SIGGRAPH, 1990, pp. 35–36.
- ⁴ Chris Joslin, Thomas Di Giacomo, and Nadia Magnenat-Thalmann. “Collaborative Virtual Environments: From Birth to Standardization”. IEEE Communications Magazine, pp 28-33, April 2004
- ⁵ Distributed Interactive Virtual Environment (DIVE). <<http://www.sics.se/dive>>.
- ⁶ Active Worlds. <<http://www.activeworlds.com>>
- ⁷ Mitsubishi Electric Research Laboratories. Scalable Platform for Large Interactive Networked Environments (SPLINE). <http://www.merl.com/projects/spline/>.
- ⁸ Oliveira, M., Crowcroft, J. and Slater, M. Component Framework Infrastructure for Virtual Environments. Proceedings of the CVE 2000 Symposium. ACM, 2000, 139-146.
- ⁹ Greenhalgh, C., Purbrick, J and Snowdon, D. Inside MASSIVE-3: Flexible Support for Data Consistency and World Structuring. Proceedings of the CVE 2000 Symposium, ACM, 2000, 119-127
- ¹⁰ Pedro García and Antonio Gómez Skarmeta. “ANTS Framework for Cooperative Work Environments”. IEEE Computer, pp 56-62, March 2003
- ¹¹ David A. Smith, Alan Kay, Andreas Raab, David P. Reed. “Croquet - A Collaboration System Architecture,” First Conference on Creating, Connecting and Collaborating through Computing, 2003, c5, p. 2
- ¹² Tixeo Soft. <<http://www.workspace3d.com>>.

- ¹⁴ Roussos, M., Johnson, A., Moher, T., Leigh, J., Vasilakis, C., and Barnes, C. (1998). “Learning and Building Together in an Immersive Virtual World In Presence” vol 8, no 3, June, 1999, special issue on Virtual Environments and Learning; edited by William Winn and Michale J Moshell., MIT Press, 1998, pp. 247-263 and cover page.
- ¹⁵ FlatLand website at <http://www.flatland.com/>
- ¹⁶ <http://www.vrml.org/technicalinfo/specifications/vrml97/index.htm>
- ¹⁷ B. Damer: Avatars! : Exploring and Building Virtual Worlds on the Internet, PeachPit Press, 1997
- ¹⁸ Barbieri Thimoty, Paolini Paolo – Broadcast and on-line cultural heritage: Reconstructing Leonardo's ideal city - from handwritten codexes to webtalk-II: a 3D collaborative virtual

environment system, Proceedings of the 2001 conference on Virtual reality, archeology, and cultural heritage, Glyfada, Greece, November 2001

¹⁹ Barbieri Thimoty – Networked Virtual Environments for the Web: The WebTalk-I and WebTalk-II Architectures , in Proceedings IEEE for Computer Multimedia & Expo 2000 (ICME) , New York, USA, July 2000

²⁰ Paolini Paolo, Barbieri Thimoty, et al. – Visiting a Museum Together: how to share a visit to a virtual world, in Proceedings Museums&Web '99, New Orleans (USA), Marzo 99, pg. 27

²¹ Honda Yasuaki, Mitra, Rockwell Bob, Roehl Bernie - «Living Worlds – Making VRML 2.0 Applications Interpersonal and Interoperable» - www.livingworlds.com

²² Roehl B. et al. – Late Night VRML 2.0 with Java Ziff-Davis Press, Emeryville, 1997

²³ Brutzman, D. – Internetworked Graphics: Capabilities, Shortfalls, Frontiers in Course Notes Internetworked 3D Computer Graphics: Overcoming Bottlenecks and supporting collaboration, SIGGRAPH 99 Los Angeles 1999

²⁴ Di Blas N., Hazan S., Paolini P. - The SEE Experience: Edutainment in 3D Virtual Worlds, in Proceedings Museums and the Web '03, Charlotte (USA)

²⁵ Barbieri Thimoty, Barchetti Ugo, Bucciero Alberto, Mainetti Luca: WebTalk Cube: a framework to add one dimension to e-learning, in Proceedings of AICA 2004, Benevento, Italy, October 2004

²⁶ Havok web site available at <http://www.havok.com/>

²⁷ FRÉCON E., STENIUS M. : DIVE: A scalable network architecture for distributed virtual environments. Distributed System Engineering Journal,5, pp. 91-100, 1998.

²⁸ GREENHALGH C., PURBTICK J., SNOWDOWN D.: Inside MASSIVE-3: Flexible support for data consistency and world structuring. In Proceedings of Collaborative Virtual Environments 2000, pp. 119-127, San Francisco, September 2000.

²⁹ DACHSELT, R.: CONTIGRA - Towards a Document-based Approach to 3D Components. In Workshop proceedings "Structured Design of Virtual Environments and 3DComponents" of the ACM Web3D 2001 Symposium, Paderborn, 2001.

³⁰ CAPPS, M., MCGREGOR, D., BRUTZMAN D., ZYDA M.: NPSNET-V. In IEEE Computer Graphics and Applications, Vol. 20, No. 5, 2000, 12-15.

³¹ WATSEN K. , ZYDA M.: Bamboo – A Portable System for Dynamically Extensible, Real-time, Networked, Virtual Environments. In Proceedings of the IEEE Virtual Reality Annual International Symposium (VRAIS'98), Atlanta, Georgia, 1998, pp. 252-259.

³² DACHSELT, R.: CONTIGRA: A High-Level XML-Based Approach to Interactive 3D Components. In SIGGRAPH 2001 Conference Abstracts and Applications, Los Angeles, August 2001, 163.

³³ X3D Specification: <http://www.web3d.org/x3d/specifications/>

- ³⁴ DACHSELT R., RUKZIO E.: BEHAVIOR3D : An XML-based framework for 3D graphics behavior. In Proceedings of the 8th International Symposium on Web3D Technologies. WEB3D Consortium, 2003.
- ³⁵ ROEHL B. 1995. Some Thoughts on Behaviour in VR Systems. <http://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~broehl/behav.html>.
- ³⁶ XML-Schema: www.w3.org/XML/Schema
- ³⁷ PETTIFER S., MARSH J. : A collaborative access model for shared virtual environments. In Proceedings of IEEE WETICE 01, pages 257-272. IEEE Computer Society, June 2001.
- ³⁸ BARBIERI T., PAOLINI P.: Cooperation Metaphors for Virtual Museums . In Proceedings Museums & Web 2001, Seattle, USA, March 2001.
- ³⁹ Johnson D.W. and Johnson, R.T. Instructional goal structure: Cooperative, competitive, or individualistic. *Review of Educational Research*, 44, pp. 213-240, 1991
- ⁴⁰ Slavin, R.E. When does cooperative learning increases student achievement? *Psychological Bulletin*, 94, pp. 429-445, 1984
- ⁴¹ Abowd, G.D., Atkeson, C.G., Hong, J., Long, S., Kooper, R., and Pinkerton, M. Cyberguide A mobile context-aware tour guide. *ACM Wireless Networks*, 5, 3, pp. 421-433, 1997.
- ⁴² Bederson, B., Hollan, J. D., Druin, A., Stewart, J., & Proft, D. (1999). Local tools: an alternative to tool palettes. In proceedings of UIST'99, ACM Press, 169-170.
- ⁴³ Danesh, A., Inkpen, K.M., Lau, F., Shu, K., and Booth, K.S. (2001) Geney: Designing a collaborative activity for the Palm handheld computer. In Proceedings of CHI, Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems. Seattle, USA, April 2001
- ⁴⁴ Inkpen, K.M. (1999). Designing Handheld Technologies for Kids. *Personal Technologies Journal*, 3 (1&2), pp. 81-89.
- ⁴⁵ Malone T.W. & Lepper M.R. (1987) Making learning fun: a taxonomic model of intrinsic motivations for learning. In *Aptitude, Learning, and Instruction: III. Conative and Affective Process Analysis* (eds R.E. Snow & M.J. Farr), pp. 223–253. Erlbaum, Hillsdale, NJ.
- ⁴⁶ Lepper M.R. & Cordova D.I. (1992) A desire to be taught: instructional consequences of intrinsic motivation. *Motivation and Emotion* 16, 187–208.
- ⁴⁷ Prensky M. (2001) *Digital Game-Based Learning*. McGraw-Hill, New York.
- ⁴⁸ Mitchell A. & Savill-Smith C. (2004) *The Use of Computer and Video Games for Learning*. Learning and Skills Development Agency, London.
- ⁴⁹ Savill-Smith C. & Kent P. (2003) *The Use of Palmtop Computers for Learning, A Review of the Literature*. LSDA, London.
- ⁵⁰ Facer K., Joiner .R., Stanton D., Reid J., Hull R. & Kirk D. (2004) Savannah: mobile gaming and learning? *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* 20, 399–409.

⁵¹ Benford S., Anastasi R., Flinham M., Drozd A., Crabtree A., Greenhalgh C., Tandavanitj N., Adams M. & Row-Farr J. (2003) Coping with uncertainty in a location-based game. *IEEE Pervasive Computing Journal* 2, 34–41.

⁵² Björk S., Fals J., Hansson R. & Ljungstrand P. (2001) Pirates! Using the physical world as a game board. Paper at Interact, IFIP TC.13 Conference on Human-Computer Interaction, July 9–13, Tokyo, Japan.

⁵³ Hall J. (2001) Mogi: Second Generation Location-Based Gaming. Available: <http://www.thefeaturearchives.com/100501.html>

⁵⁴ M. Stefik, D. G. Bobrow, S. Lanning, and D. Tatar, WYSIWIS revised: Early experiences with multiuser interfaces. *ACM Transactions on Information Systems*, Vol.5, No.2, pp.147-167, April 1987.

⁵⁵ Greenberg S., Gutwin C., and Cockburn, A. Sharing fisheye views in relaxed-WYSIWIS groupware applications In *Proceedings of Graphics Interface*, Toronto, Canada, pp28-38, May 22-24, 1995

⁵⁶ Chang, K. H., Gong, Y., Dollar, T., Gajiwala, S., Lee, Byong and Wear A. W., On Computer Supported Collaborative Writing Tools for Distributed Environments. In *Proceedings of ACM 23rd Conference on Computer Science*, pp222-229, Feb. 1995

⁵⁷ <http://www.blaxxun.com>